

Alternative Layouts for Grid Questions in PC and Mobile Web Surveys: An Experimental Evaluation Using Response Quality Indicators and Survey Estimates

Pairwise Comparisons (Estimated Marginal Means)

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The pairwise comparisons were performed with Bonferroni adjustments for multiple comparisons and are the basis of summary tables with ANOVA results.

1 Pairwise comparisons for RQIs

1.1 Unit-level item nonresponse

Table 1: Estimated marginal means for item nonresponse by layout

Item nonresponse: Mean differences between the layouts within each device							
Dependent Variable: exposed item nonresponse percentage							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	-0.001	0.002	1.000	-0.006	0.004
		Unfolding	-0.002	0.002	1.000	-0.007	0.003
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.007*	0.002	0.000	-0.012	-0.002
		Paging	0.001	0.002	1.000	-0.003	0.006
	Scrolling	Grid	0.001	0.002	1.000	-0.004	0.006
		Unfolding	-0.001	0.002	1.000	-0.006	0.004
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.006*	0.002	0.003	-0.011	-0.001
		Paging	0.002	0.002	1.000	-0.003	0.007
	Unfolding	Grid	0.002	0.002	1.000	-0.003	0.007
		Scrolling	0.001	0.002	1.000	-0.004	0.006
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.005*	0.002	0.027	-0.010	0.000
		Paging	0.003	0.002	0.471	-0.001	0.008
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.007*	0.002	0.000	0.002	0.012
		Scrolling	0.006*	0.002	0.003	0.001	0.011
		Unfolding	0.005*	0.002	0.027	0.000	0.010
		Paging	0.009*	0.002	0.000	0.004	0.014
	Paging	Grid	-0.001	0.002	1.000	-0.006	0.003
		Scrolling	-0.002	0.002	1.000	-0.007	0.003
		Unfolding	-0.003	0.002	0.471	-0.008	0.001
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.009*	0.002	0.000	-0.014	-0.004
SP	Grid	Scrolling	0.003	0.002	1.000	-0.003	0.008
		Unfolding	0.002	0.002	1.000	-0.003	0.007

		Horizontal scrolling	-0.013*	0.002	0.000	-0.018	-0.008
		Paging	0.003	0.002	0.751	-0.002	0.009
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.003	0.002	1.000	-0.008	0.003
		Unfolding	-0.001	0.002	1.000	-0.006	0.005
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.016*	0.002	0.000	-0.021	-0.010
		Paging	0.001	0.002	1.000	-0.004	0.006
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.002	0.002	1.000	-0.007	0.003
		Scrolling	0.001	0.002	1.000	-0.005	0.006
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.015*	0.002	0.000	-0.021	-0.010
		Paging	0.001	0.002	1.000	-0.004	0.007
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.013*	0.002	0.000	0.008	0.018
		Scrolling	0.016*	0.002	0.000	0.010	0.021
		Unfolding	0.015*	0.002	0.000	0.010	0.021
		Paging	0.017*	0.002	0.000	0.011	0.022
	Paging	Grid	-0.003	0.002	0.751	-0.009	0.002
		Scrolling	-0.001	0.002	1.000	-0.006	0.004
		Unfolding	-0.001	0.002	1.000	-0.007	0.004
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.017*	0.002	0.000	-0.022	-0.011
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 2: Estimated marginal means for item nonresponse by device

Item nonresponse: Mean differences between the devices within each layout							
Dependent Variable: exposed item nonresponse percentage							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	-0.001	0.002	0.420	-0.005	0.002
	SP	PC	0.001	0.002	0.420	-0.002	0.005
Scrolling	PC	SP	0.002	0.002	0.273	-0.002	0.006
	SP	PC	-0.002	0.002	0.273	-0.006	0.002
Unfolding	PC	SP	0.003	0.002	0.165	-0.001	0.006
	SP	PC	-0.003	0.002	0.165	-0.006	0.001
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	-0.007*	0.002	0.000	-0.011	-0.004
	SP	PC	0.007*	0.002	0.000	0.004	0.011
Paging	PC	SP	0.000	0.002	0.804	-0.003	0.004
	SP	PC	0.000	0.002	0.804	-0.004	0.003
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

1.2 Straightlining

Table 3: Estimated marginal means for straightlining by layout

Straightlining: Mean differences between the layouts within each device							
Dependent Variable: ATT number of grids with sd0							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	0.065	0.043	1.000	-0.054	0.185
		Unfolding	0.068	0.043	1.000	-0.052	0.187
		Horizontal scrolling	0.058	0.043	1.000	-0.062	0.179
		Paging	0.167*	0.043	0.001	0.048	0.287
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.065	0.043	1.000	-0.185	0.054
		Unfolding	0.002	0.042	1.000	-0.116	0.121
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.007	0.043	1.000	-0.127	0.112
		Paging	0.102	0.042	0.159	-0.017	0.220
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.068	0.043	1.000	-0.187	0.052
		Scrolling	-0.002	0.042	1.000	-0.121	0.116
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.009	0.042	1.000	-0.129	0.110
		Paging	0.100	0.042	0.181	-0.019	0.218
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.058	0.043	1.000	-0.179	0.062
		Scrolling	0.007	0.043	1.000	-0.112	0.127
		Unfolding	0.009	0.042	1.000	-0.110	0.129
		Paging	0.109	0.042	0.101	-0.010	0.228
	Paging	Grid	-0.167*	0.043	0.001	-0.287	-0.048
		Scrolling	-0.102	0.042	0.159	-0.220	0.017
		Unfolding	-0.100	0.042	0.181	-0.218	0.019
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.109	0.042	0.101	-0.228	0.010
SP	Grid	Scrolling	0.112	0.046	0.159	-0.018	0.242
		Unfolding	0.115	0.047	0.147	-0.017	0.247
		Horizontal scrolling	0.072	0.047	1.000	-0.060	0.204
		Paging	0.174*	0.048	0.003	0.040	0.308
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.112	0.046	0.159	-0.242	0.018
		Unfolding	0.003	0.047	1.000	-0.129	0.135
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.040	0.047	1.000	-0.172	0.091
		Paging	0.062	0.048	1.000	-0.072	0.196
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.115	0.047	0.147	-0.247	0.017
		Scrolling	-0.003	0.047	1.000	-0.135	0.129
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.043	0.048	1.000	-0.177	0.090
		Paging	0.059	0.048	1.000	-0.077	0.195
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.072	0.047	1.000	-0.204	0.060
		Scrolling	0.040	0.047	1.000	-0.091	0.172
		Unfolding	0.043	0.048	1.000	-0.090	0.177
		Paging	0.102	0.048	0.338	-0.033	0.238
	Paging	Grid	-0.174*	0.048	0.003	-0.308	-0.040
		Scrolling	-0.062	0.048	1.000	-0.196	0.072
		Unfolding	-0.059	0.048	1.000	-0.195	0.077
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.102	0.048	0.338	-0.238	0.033
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 4: Estimated marginal means for straightlining by device

Straightlining: Mean differences between the devices within each layout							
Dependent Variable: ATT number of grids with sd0							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	-0.009	0.045	0.835	-0.097	0.078
	SP	PC	0.009	0.045	0.835	-0.078	0.097
Scrolling	PC	SP	0.037	0.044	0.402	-0.050	0.124
	SP	PC	-0.037	0.044	0.402	-0.124	0.050
Unfolding	PC	SP	0.038	0.045	0.399	-0.050	0.126
	SP	PC	-0.038	0.045	0.399	-0.126	0.050
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	0.004	0.045	0.929	-0.085	0.093
	SP	PC	-0.004	0.045	0.929	-0.093	0.085
Paging	PC	SP	-0.003	0.046	0.955	-0.092	0.087
	SP	PC	0.003	0.046	0.955	-0.087	0.092

Based on estimated marginal means

a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.

1.3 Extreme and midpoint responses

Table 5: Estimated marginal means for midpoint responses by layout

Midpoint responses: Mean differences between the layouts within each device							
Dependent Variable: ATT overall grid mean midpoint response percentage							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	0.008	0.012	1.000	-0.026	0.041
		Unfolding	-0.004	0.012	1.000	-0.037	0.029
		Horizontal scrolling	0.012	0.012	1.000	-0.021	0.046
		Paging	0.008	0.012	1.000	-0.025	0.041
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.008	0.012	1.000	-0.041	0.026
		Unfolding	-0.012	0.012	1.000	-0.045	0.021
		Horizontal scrolling	0.005	0.012	1.000	-0.029	0.038
		Paging	0.000	0.012	1.000	-0.033	0.033
	Unfolding	Grid	0.004	0.012	1.000	-0.029	0.037
		Scrolling	0.012	0.012	1.000	-0.021	0.045
		Horizontal scrolling	0.016	0.012	1.000	-0.017	0.049
		Paging	0.012	0.012	1.000	-0.021	0.045
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.012	0.012	1.000	-0.046	0.021
		Scrolling	-0.005	0.012	1.000	-0.038	0.029
		Unfolding	-0.016	0.012	1.000	-0.049	0.017
		Paging	-0.004	0.012	1.000	-0.037	0.029
	Paging	Grid	-0.008	0.012	1.000	-0.041	0.025
		Scrolling	0.000	0.012	1.000	-0.033	0.033
		Unfolding	-0.012	0.012	1.000	-0.045	0.021
		Horizontal scrolling	0.004	0.012	1.000	-0.029	0.037
SP	Grid	Scrolling	0.010	0.013	1.000	-0.026	0.046
		Unfolding	0.012	0.013	1.000	-0.025	0.049
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.021	0.013	1.000	-0.057	0.016
		Paging	0.020	0.013	1.000	-0.018	0.057
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.010	0.013	1.000	-0.046	0.026
		Unfolding	0.002	0.013	1.000	-0.034	0.039
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.030	0.013	0.199	-0.067	0.006
		Paging	0.010	0.013	1.000	-0.027	0.047
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.012	0.013	1.000	-0.049	0.025
		Scrolling	-0.002	0.013	1.000	-0.039	0.034
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.033	0.013	0.132	-0.070	0.004
		Paging	0.007	0.013	1.000	-0.030	0.045
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.021	0.013	1.000	-0.016	0.057
		Scrolling	0.030	0.013	0.199	-0.006	0.067
		Unfolding	0.033	0.013	0.132	-0.004	0.070
		Paging	0.040*	0.013	0.027	0.003	0.078
	Paging	Grid	-0.020	0.013	1.000	-0.057	0.018
		Scrolling	-0.010	0.013	1.000	-0.047	0.027
		Unfolding	-0.007	0.013	1.000	-0.045	0.030
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.040*	0.013	0.027	-0.078	-0.003
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 6: Estimated marginal means for midpoint responses by device

Midpoint responses: Mean differences between the devices within each layout							
Dependent Variable: ATT overall grid mean midpoint response percentage							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	0.009	0.012	0.470	-0.015	0.033
	SP	PC	-0.009	0.012	0.470	-0.033	0.015
Scrolling	PC	SP	0.011	0.012	0.374	-0.013	0.035
	SP	PC	-0.011	0.012	0.374	-0.035	0.013
Unfolding	PC	SP	0.025*	0.012	0.044	0.001	0.050
	SP	PC	-0.025*	0.012	0.044	-0.050	-0.001
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	-0.024	0.013	0.057	-0.049	0.001
	SP	PC	0.024	0.013	0.057	-0.001	0.049
Paging	PC	SP	0.020	0.013	0.108	-0.004	0.045
	SP	PC	-0.020	0.013	0.108	-0.045	0.004
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 7: Estimated marginal means for extreme positive responses by layout

Extreme positive responses: Mean differences between the layouts within each device							
Dependent Variable: ATT overall grid mean extreme POSITIVE response percentage							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	0.010	0.007	1.000	-0.009	0.029
		Unfolding	0.012	0.007	0.871	-0.007	0.030
		Horizontal scrolling	0.018	0.007	0.079	-0.001	0.037
		Paging	0.017	0.007	0.111	-0.002	0.036
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.010	0.007	1.000	-0.029	0.009
		Unfolding	0.001	0.007	1.000	-0.018	0.020
		Horizontal scrolling	0.008	0.007	1.000	-0.011	0.027
		Paging	0.007	0.007	1.000	-0.012	0.026
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.012	0.007	0.871	-0.030	0.007
		Scrolling	-0.001	0.007	1.000	-0.020	0.018
		Horizontal scrolling	0.006	0.007	1.000	-0.012	0.025
		Paging	0.006	0.007	1.000	-0.013	0.024
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.018	0.007	0.079	-0.037	0.001
		Scrolling	-0.008	0.007	1.000	-0.027	0.011
		Unfolding	-0.006	0.007	1.000	-0.025	0.012
		Paging	-0.001	0.007	1.000	-0.020	0.018
	Paging	Grid	-0.017	0.007	0.111	-0.036	0.002
		Scrolling	-0.007	0.007	1.000	-0.026	0.012
		Unfolding	-0.006	0.007	1.000	-0.024	0.013
		Horizontal scrolling	0.001	0.007	1.000	-0.018	0.020
SP	Grid	Scrolling	0.011	0.007	1.000	-0.009	0.032
		Unfolding	0.017	0.007	0.256	-0.004	0.038
		Horizontal scrolling	0.021*	0.007	0.041	0.000	0.042
		Paging	0.009	0.008	1.000	-0.012	0.030
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.011	0.007	1.000	-0.032	0.009
		Unfolding	0.005	0.007	1.000	-0.016	0.026
		Horizontal scrolling	0.010	0.007	1.000	-0.011	0.031
		Paging	-0.003	0.008	1.000	-0.024	0.019
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.017	0.007	0.256	-0.038	0.004
		Scrolling	-0.005	0.007	1.000	-0.026	0.016
		Horizontal scrolling	0.005	0.008	1.000	-0.016	0.026
		Paging	-0.008	0.008	1.000	-0.029	0.014
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.021*	0.007	0.041	-0.042	0.000
		Scrolling	-0.010	0.007	1.000	-0.031	0.011
		Unfolding	-0.005	0.008	1.000	-0.026	0.016
		Paging	-0.013	0.008	0.971	-0.034	0.009
	Paging	Grid	-0.009	0.008	1.000	-0.030	0.012
		Scrolling	0.003	0.008	1.000	-0.019	0.024
		Unfolding	0.008	0.008	1.000	-0.014	0.029
		Horizontal scrolling	0.013	0.008	0.971	-0.009	0.034
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 8: Estimated marginal means for extreme positive responses by device

Extreme positive responses: Mean differences between the devices within each layout							
Dependent Variable: ATT overall grid mean extreme POSITIVE response percentage							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	-0.014	0.007	0.052	-0.028	0.000
	SP	PC	0.014	0.007	0.052	0.000	0.028
Scrolling	PC	SP	-0.013	0.007	0.071	-0.027	0.001
	SP	PC	0.013	0.007	0.071	-0.001	0.027
Unfolding	PC	SP	-0.009	0.007	0.222	-0.023	0.005
	SP	PC	0.009	0.007	0.222	-0.005	0.023
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	-0.010	0.007	0.144	-0.024	0.004
	SP	PC	0.010	0.007	0.144	-0.004	0.024
Paging	PC	SP	-0.022*	0.007	0.002	-0.036	-0.008
	SP	PC	0.022*	0.007	0.002	0.008	0.036
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 9: Estimated marginal means for extreme negative responses by layout

Extreme negative responses: Mean differences between the layouts within each device							
Dependent Variable: ATT overall grid mean extreme NEGATIVE response percentage							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	0.019	0.008	0.189	-0.004	0.041
		Unfolding	0.017	0.008	0.359	-0.006	0.039
		Horizontal scrolling	0.020	0.008	0.128	-0.003	0.043
		Paging	0.011	0.008	1.000	-0.011	0.034
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.019	0.008	0.189	-0.041	0.004
		Unfolding	-0.002	0.008	1.000	-0.024	0.020
		Horizontal scrolling	0.001	0.008	1.000	-0.021	0.024
		Paging	-0.007	0.008	1.000	-0.030	0.015
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.017	0.008	0.359	-0.039	0.006
		Scrolling	0.002	0.008	1.000	-0.020	0.024
		Horizontal scrolling	0.003	0.008	1.000	-0.019	0.026
		Paging	-0.005	0.008	1.000	-0.028	0.017
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.020	0.008	0.128	-0.043	0.003
		Scrolling	-0.001	0.008	1.000	-0.024	0.021
		Unfolding	-0.003	0.008	1.000	-0.026	0.019
		Paging	-0.009	0.008	1.000	-0.031	0.014
	Paging	Grid	-0.011	0.008	1.000	-0.034	0.011
		Scrolling	0.007	0.008	1.000	-0.015	0.030
		Unfolding	0.005	0.008	1.000	-0.017	0.028
		Horizontal scrolling	0.009	0.008	1.000	-0.014	0.031
SP	Grid	Scrolling	0.023	0.009	0.089	-0.002	0.047
		Unfolding	0.026*	0.009	0.038	0.001	0.050
		Horizontal scrolling	0.034*	0.009	0.001	0.009	0.059
		Paging	0.009	0.009	1.000	-0.017	0.034
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.023	0.009	0.089	-0.047	0.002
		Unfolding	0.003	0.009	1.000	-0.022	0.027
		Horizontal scrolling	0.011	0.009	1.000	-0.013	0.036
		Paging	-0.014	0.009	1.000	-0.039	0.011
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.026*	0.009	0.038	-0.050	-0.001
		Scrolling	-0.003	0.009	1.000	-0.027	0.022
		Horizontal scrolling	0.009	0.009	1.000	-0.016	0.034
		Paging	-0.017	0.009	0.599	-0.042	0.008
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.034*	0.009	0.001	-0.059	-0.009
		Scrolling	-0.011	0.009	1.000	-0.036	0.013
		Unfolding	-0.009	0.009	1.000	-0.034	0.016
		Paging	-0.026*	0.009	0.046	-0.051	0.000
	Paging	Grid	-0.009	0.009	1.000	-0.034	0.017
		Scrolling	0.014	0.009	1.000	-0.011	0.039
		Unfolding	0.017	0.009	0.599	-0.008	0.042
		Horizontal scrolling	0.026*	0.009	0.046	0.000	0.051
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 10: Estimated marginal means for extreme negative responses by device

Extreme negative responses: Mean differences between the devices within each layout							
Dependent Variable: ATT overall grid mean extreme NEGATIVE response percentage							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	-0.004	0.008	0.675	-0.020	0.013
	SP	PC	0.004	0.008	0.675	-0.013	0.020
Scrolling	PC	SP	0.000	0.008	0.954	-0.016	0.017
	SP	PC	0.000	0.008	0.954	-0.017	0.016
Unfolding	PC	SP	0.005	0.008	0.532	-0.011	0.022
	SP	PC	-0.005	0.008	0.532	-0.022	0.011
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	0.011	0.008	0.212	-0.006	0.027
	SP	PC	-0.011	0.008	0.212	-0.027	0.006
Paging	PC	SP	-0.006	0.009	0.457	-0.023	0.010
	SP	PC	0.006	0.009	0.457	-0.010	0.023
Based on estimated marginal means							
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

1.4 Concurrent multitasking

Table 11: Estimated marginal means for concurrent multitasking by layout

Concurrent multitasking: Mean differences between the layouts within each device							
Dependent Variable: Concurrent MT, number							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	-0.003	0.032	1.000	-0.093	0.087
		Unfolding	0.003	0.032	1.000	-0.087	0.093
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.007	0.032	1.000	-0.097	0.083
		Paging	-0.073	0.032	0.226	-0.163	0.017
	Scrolling	Grid	0.003	0.032	1.000	-0.087	0.093
		Unfolding	0.006	0.032	1.000	-0.084	0.095
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.004	0.032	1.000	-0.094	0.086
		Paging	-0.070	0.032	0.275	-0.160	0.019
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.003	0.032	1.000	-0.093	0.087
		Scrolling	-0.006	0.032	1.000	-0.095	0.084
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.010	0.032	1.000	-0.099	0.080
		Paging	-0.076	0.032	0.167	-0.165	0.013
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.007	0.032	1.000	-0.083	0.097
		Scrolling	0.004	0.032	1.000	-0.086	0.094
		Unfolding	0.010	0.032	1.000	-0.080	0.099
		Paging	-0.066	0.032	0.383	-0.156	0.024
	Paging	Grid	0.073	0.032	0.226	-0.017	0.163
		Scrolling	0.070	0.032	0.275	-0.019	0.160
		Unfolding	0.076	0.032	0.167	-0.013	0.165
		Horizontal scrolling	0.066	0.032	0.383	-0.024	0.156
SP	Grid	Scrolling	-0.056	0.035	1.000	-0.155	0.044
		Unfolding	-0.034	0.036	1.000	-0.135	0.068
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.102*	0.036	0.044	-0.203	-0.001
		Paging	-0.054	0.037	1.000	-0.158	0.049
	Scrolling	Grid	0.056	0.035	1.000	-0.044	0.155
		Unfolding	0.022	0.036	1.000	-0.079	0.123
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.047	0.036	1.000	-0.147	0.054
		Paging	0.002	0.037	1.000	-0.101	0.104
	Unfolding	Grid	0.034	0.036	1.000	-0.068	0.135
		Scrolling	-0.022	0.036	1.000	-0.123	0.079
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.069	0.037	0.599	-0.171	0.034
		Paging	-0.021	0.037	1.000	-0.126	0.084
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.102*	0.036	0.044	0.001	0.203
		Scrolling	0.047	0.036	1.000	-0.054	0.147
		Unfolding	0.069	0.037	0.599	-0.034	0.171
		Paging	0.048	0.037	1.000	-0.056	0.152
	Paging	Grid	0.054	0.037	1.000	-0.049	0.158
		Scrolling	-0.002	0.037	1.000	-0.104	0.101
		Unfolding	0.021	0.037	1.000	-0.084	0.126
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.048	0.037	1.000	-0.152	0.056
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 12: Estimated marginal means for concurrent multitasking by device

Concurrent multitasking: Mean differences between the devices within each layout							
Dependent Variable: Concurrent MT, number							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	0.053	0.034	0.119	-0.014	0.119
	SP	PC	-0.053	0.034	0.119	-0.119	0.014
Scrolling	PC	SP	0.000	0.034	0.996	-0.066	0.066
	SP	PC	0.000	0.034	0.996	-0.066	0.066
Unfolding	PC	SP	0.016	0.034	0.633	-0.051	0.084
	SP	PC	-0.016	0.034	0.633	-0.084	0.051
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	-0.043	0.034	0.214	-0.110	0.025
	SP	PC	0.043	0.034	0.214	-0.025	0.110
Paging	PC	SP	0.072*	0.035	0.041	0.003	0.141
	SP	PC	-0.072*	0.035	0.041	-0.141	-0.003
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

1.5 Sequential multitasking

Table 13: Estimated marginal means for sequential multitasking by layout

Sequential multitasking: Mean differences between the layouts within each device							
Dependent Variable: Sequential MT, number							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	0.008	0.037	1.000	-0.096	0.112
		Unfolding	-0.060	0.037	1.000	-0.164	0.044
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.016	0.037	1.000	-0.121	0.088
		Paging	-0.078	0.037	0.351	-0.182	0.026
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.008	0.037	1.000	-0.112	0.096
		Unfolding	-0.068	0.037	0.643	-0.171	0.035
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.024	0.037	1.000	-0.128	0.080
		Paging	-0.086	0.037	0.196	-0.190	0.017
	Unfolding	Grid	0.060	0.037	1.000	-0.044	0.164
		Scrolling	0.068	0.037	0.643	-0.035	0.171
		Horizontal scrolling	0.044	0.037	1.000	-0.060	0.147
		Paging	-0.018	0.037	1.000	-0.121	0.085
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.016	0.037	1.000	-0.088	0.121
		Scrolling	0.024	0.037	1.000	-0.080	0.128
		Unfolding	-0.044	0.037	1.000	-0.147	0.060
		Paging	-0.062	0.037	0.940	-0.166	0.042
	Paging	Grid	0.078	0.037	0.351	-0.026	0.182
		Scrolling	0.086	0.037	0.196	-0.017	0.190
		Unfolding	0.018	0.037	1.000	-0.085	0.121
		Horizontal scrolling	0.062	0.037	0.940	-0.042	0.166
SP	Grid	Scrolling	0.011	0.041	1.000	-0.104	0.126
		Unfolding	0.047	0.042	1.000	-0.070	0.165
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.020	0.042	1.000	-0.136	0.097
		Paging	-0.031	0.042	1.000	-0.150	0.088
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.011	0.041	1.000	-0.126	0.104
		Unfolding	0.036	0.042	1.000	-0.080	0.153
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.030	0.041	1.000	-0.147	0.086
		Paging	-0.042	0.042	1.000	-0.161	0.077
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.047	0.042	1.000	-0.165	0.070
		Scrolling	-0.036	0.042	1.000	-0.153	0.080
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.067	0.042	1.000	-0.185	0.052
		Paging	-0.078	0.043	0.692	-0.199	0.043
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.020	0.042	1.000	-0.097	0.136
		Scrolling	0.030	0.041	1.000	-0.086	0.147
		Unfolding	0.067	0.042	1.000	-0.052	0.185
		Paging	-0.012	0.043	1.000	-0.132	0.109
	Paging	Grid	0.031	0.042	1.000	-0.088	0.150
		Scrolling	0.042	0.042	1.000	-0.077	0.161
		Unfolding	0.078	0.043	0.692	-0.043	0.199
		Horizontal scrolling	0.012	0.043	1.000	-0.109	0.132
Based on estimated marginal means							
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 14: Estimated marginal means for sequential multitasking by layout

Sequential multitasking: Mean differences between the devices within each layout							
Dependent Variable: Sequential MT, number							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	-0.011	0.039	0.770	-0.088	0.065
	SP	PC	0.011	0.039	0.770	-0.065	0.088
Scrolling	PC	SP	-0.009	0.039	0.824	-0.085	0.068
	SP	PC	0.009	0.039	0.824	-0.068	0.085
Unfolding	PC	SP	0.096*	0.040	0.016	0.018	0.173
	SP	PC	-0.096*	0.040	0.016	-0.173	-0.018
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	-0.015	0.040	0.708	-0.092	0.063
	SP	PC	0.015	0.040	0.708	-0.063	0.092
Paging	PC	SP	0.036	0.040	0.379	-0.044	0.115
	SP	PC	-0.036	0.040	0.379	-0.115	0.044
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

1.6 Grid duration

Table 15: Estimated marginal means for grid duration by layout

Grid duration: Mean differences between the layouts within each device							
Dependent Variable: NB_dur2_foc_p99							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	-89.191*	28.692	0.019	-169.771	-8.610
		Unfolding	-35.216	28.602	1.000	-115.543	45.112
		Horizontal scrolling	-114.713*	28.769	0.001	-195.509	-33.917
		Paging	-766.488*	28.692	0.000	-847.068	-685.907
	Scrolling	Grid	89.191*	28.692	0.019	8.610	169.771
		Unfolding	53.975	28.509	0.584	-26.092	134.042
		Horizontal scrolling	-25.522	28.676	1.000	-106.059	55.015
		Paging	-677.297*	28.599	0.000	-757.618	-596.976
	Unfolding	Grid	35.216	28.602	1.000	-45.112	115.543
		Scrolling	-53.975	28.509	0.584	-134.042	26.092
		Horizontal scrolling	-79.497	28.586	0.054	-159.780	0.786
		Paging	-731.272*	28.509	0.000	-811.339	-651.205
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	114.713*	28.769	0.001	33.917	195.509
		Scrolling	25.522	28.676	1.000	-55.015	106.059
		Unfolding	79.497	28.586	0.054	-0.786	159.780
		Paging	-651.775*	28.676	0.000	-732.312	-571.238
	Paging	Grid	766.488*	28.692	0.000	685.907	847.068
		Scrolling	677.297*	28.599	0.000	596.976	757.618
		Unfolding	731.272*	28.509	0.000	651.205	811.339
		Horizontal scrolling	651.775*	28.676	0.000	571.238	732.312
SP	Grid	Scrolling	-15.820	30.666	1.000	-101.945	70.306
		Unfolding	-17.328	31.251	1.000	-105.095	70.439
		Horizontal scrolling	-133.063*	30.872	0.000	-219.766	-46.361
		Paging	-633.706*	31.335	0.000	-721.709	-545.703
	Scrolling	Grid	15.820	30.666	1.000	-70.306	101.945
		Unfolding	-1.509	31.029	1.000	-88.652	85.635
		Horizontal scrolling	-117.244*	30.647	0.001	-203.315	-31.173
		Paging	-617.886*	31.113	0.000	-705.267	-530.505
	Unfolding	Grid	17.328	31.251	1.000	-70.439	105.095
		Scrolling	1.509	31.029	1.000	-85.635	88.652
		Horizontal scrolling	-115.735*	31.232	0.002	-203.449	-28.021
		Paging	-616.377*	31.690	0.000	-705.377	-527.378
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	133.063*	30.872	0.000	46.361	219.766
		Scrolling	117.244*	30.647	0.001	31.173	203.315
		Unfolding	115.735*	31.232	0.002	28.021	203.449
		Paging	-500.642*	31.316	0.000	-588.592	-412.693
	Paging	Grid	633.706*	31.335	0.000	545.703	721.709
		Scrolling	617.886*	31.113	0.000	530.505	705.267
		Unfolding	616.377*	31.690	0.000	527.378	705.377
		Horizontal scrolling	500.642*	31.316	0.000	412.693	588.592
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 16: Estimated marginal means for grid duration by device

Grid duration: Mean differences between the devices within each layout							
Dependent Variable: NB_dur2_foc_p99							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	13.871	29.856	0.642	-44.662	72.404
	SP	PC	-13.871	29.856	0.642	-72.404	44.662
Scrolling	PC	SP	87.242*	29.534	0.003	29.340	145.144
	SP	PC	-87.242*	29.534	0.003	-145.144	-29.340
Unfolding	PC	SP	31.758	30.055	0.291	-27.164	90.681
	SP	PC	-31.758	30.055	0.291	-90.681	27.164
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	-4.480	29.821	0.881	-62.945	53.985
	SP	PC	4.480	29.821	0.881	-53.985	62.945
Paging	PC	SP	146.653*	30.228	0.000	87.391	205.914
	SP	PC	-146.653*	30.228	0.000	-205.914	-87.391
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

1.7 Burden evaluation

Table 17: Estimated marginal means for self-reported burden by layout

Self-reported burden: Mean differences between the layouts within each device							
Dependent Variable: How burdensome was it to complete this survey?							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	0.133	0.062	0.312	-0.040	0.306
		Unfolding	0.116	0.061	0.591	-0.056	0.288
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.016	0.062	1.000	-0.190	0.157
		Paging	-0.297*	0.062	0.000	-0.470	-0.124
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.133	0.062	0.312	-0.306	0.040
		Unfolding	-0.017	0.061	1.000	-0.188	0.154
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.149	0.061	0.151	-0.322	0.023
		Paging	-0.430*	0.061	0.000	-0.602	-0.258
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.116	0.061	0.591	-0.288	0.056
		Scrolling	0.017	0.061	1.000	-0.154	0.188
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.132	0.061	0.306	-0.304	0.039
		Paging	-0.413*	0.061	0.000	-0.584	-0.242
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.016	0.062	1.000	-0.157	0.190
		Scrolling	0.149	0.061	0.151	-0.023	0.322
		Unfolding	0.132	0.061	0.306	-0.039	0.304
		Paging	-0.281*	0.061	0.000	-0.453	-0.108
	Paging	Grid	0.297*	0.062	0.000	0.124	0.470
		Scrolling	0.430*	0.061	0.000	0.258	0.602
		Unfolding	0.413*	0.061	0.000	0.242	0.584
		Horizontal scrolling	0.281*	0.061	0.000	0.108	0.453
SP	Grid	Scrolling	0.067	0.068	1.000	-0.124	0.257
		Unfolding	-0.122	0.069	0.774	-0.316	0.072
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.040	0.069	1.000	-0.233	0.154
		Paging	-0.379*	0.070	0.000	-0.577	-0.182
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.067	0.068	1.000	-0.257	0.124
		Unfolding	-0.189	0.069	0.062	-0.383	0.005
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.106	0.069	1.000	-0.299	0.087
		Paging	-0.446*	0.070	0.000	-0.643	-0.249
	Unfolding	Grid	0.122	0.069	0.774	-0.072	0.316
		Scrolling	0.189	0.069	0.062	-0.005	0.383
		Horizontal scrolling	0.082	0.070	1.000	-0.114	0.279
		Paging	-0.257*	0.071	0.003	-0.458	-0.057
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.040	0.069	1.000	-0.154	0.233
		Scrolling	0.106	0.069	1.000	-0.087	0.299
		Unfolding	-0.082	0.070	1.000	-0.279	0.114
		Paging	-0.340*	0.071	0.000	-0.539	-0.140
	Paging	Grid	0.379*	0.070	0.000	0.182	0.577
		Scrolling	0.446*	0.070	0.000	0.249	0.643
		Unfolding	0.257*	0.071	0.003	0.057	0.458
		Horizontal scrolling	0.340*	0.071	0.000	0.140	0.539
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 18: Estimated marginal means for self-reported burden by device

Self-reported effort: Mean differences between the devices within each layout							
Dependent Variable: How burdensome was it to complete this survey?							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	0.041	0.065	0.528	-0.086	0.168
	SP	PC	-0.041	0.065	0.528	-0.168	0.086
Scrolling	PC	SP	-0.025	0.065	0.697	-0.152	0.101
	SP	PC	0.025	0.065	0.697	-0.101	0.152
Unfolding	PC	SP	-0.197*	0.066	0.003	-0.326	-0.068
	SP	PC	0.197*	0.066	0.003	0.068	0.326
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	0.018	0.066	0.788	-0.111	0.147
	SP	PC	-0.018	0.066	0.788	-0.147	0.111
Paging	PC	SP	-0.041	0.067	0.538	-0.173	0.090
	SP	PC	0.041	0.067	0.538	-0.090	0.173
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

1.8 Instructional manipulation check

Table 19: Estimated marginal means for instructional manipulation check by layout

Instructional manipulation check: Mean differences between the layouts within each device							
Dependent Variable: Number of traps failed at level 1							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	-0.029	0.030	1.000	-0.112	0.055
		Unfolding	0.015	0.030	1.000	-0.068	0.099
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.013	0.030	1.000	-0.098	0.071
		Paging	0.024	0.030	1.000	-0.058	0.107
	Scrolling	Grid	0.029	0.030	1.000	-0.055	0.112
		Unfolding	0.044	0.030	1.000	-0.039	0.127
		Horizontal scrolling	0.015	0.030	1.000	-0.069	0.099
		Paging	0.053	0.029	0.714	-0.030	0.136
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.015	0.030	1.000	-0.099	0.068
		Scrolling	-0.044	0.030	1.000	-0.127	0.039
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.029	0.030	1.000	-0.113	0.055
		Paging	0.009	0.029	1.000	-0.073	0.091
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.013	0.030	1.000	-0.071	0.098
		Scrolling	-0.015	0.030	1.000	-0.099	0.069
		Unfolding	0.029	0.030	1.000	-0.055	0.113
		Paging	0.038	0.030	1.000	-0.046	0.121
	Paging	Grid	-0.024	0.030	1.000	-0.107	0.058
		Scrolling	-0.053	0.029	0.714	-0.136	0.030
		Unfolding	-0.009	0.029	1.000	-0.091	0.073
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.038	0.030	1.000	-0.121	0.046
SP	Grid	Scrolling	0.047	0.032	1.000	-0.043	0.137
		Unfolding	0.087	0.033	0.075	-0.004	0.179
		Horizontal scrolling	0.017	0.032	1.000	-0.074	0.108
		Paging	0.067	0.033	0.424	-0.026	0.159
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.047	0.032	1.000	-0.137	0.043
		Unfolding	0.040	0.032	1.000	-0.050	0.131
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.030	0.032	1.000	-0.120	0.059
		Paging	0.019	0.032	1.000	-0.071	0.110
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.087	0.033	0.075	-0.179	0.004
		Scrolling	-0.040	0.032	1.000	-0.131	0.050
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.071	0.033	0.296	-0.162	0.021
		Paging	-0.021	0.033	1.000	-0.113	0.072
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.017	0.032	1.000	-0.108	0.074
		Scrolling	0.030	0.032	1.000	-0.059	0.120
		Unfolding	0.071	0.033	0.296	-0.021	0.162
		Paging	0.050	0.033	1.000	-0.042	0.141
	Paging	Grid	-0.067	0.033	0.424	-0.159	0.026
		Scrolling	-0.019	0.032	1.000	-0.110	0.071
		Unfolding	0.021	0.033	1.000	-0.072	0.113
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.050	0.033	1.000	-0.141	0.042
Based on estimated marginal means							
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 20: Estimated marginal means for instructional manipulation check by device

Instructional manipulation check: Mean differences between the devices within each layout							
Dependent Variable: Number of traps failed at level 1							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	-0.074*	0.031	0.019	-0.135	-0.012
	SP	PC	0.074*	0.031	0.019	0.012	0.135
Scrolling	PC	SP	0.002	0.031	0.939	-0.058	0.062
	SP	PC	-0.002	0.031	0.939	-0.062	0.058
Unfolding	PC	SP	-0.002	0.031	0.962	-0.063	0.060
	SP	PC	0.002	0.031	0.962	-0.060	0.063
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	-0.043	0.031	0.165	-0.104	0.018
	SP	PC	0.043	0.031	0.165	-0.018	0.104
Paging	PC	SP	-0.031	0.031	0.314	-0.093	0.030
	SP	PC	0.031	0.031	0.314	-0.030	0.093
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

2 Pairwise comparisons for estimates

2.1 “Big Five” Personality Dimensions

Table 21: Estimated marginal means for “Extraversion” by layout

Pairwise Comparisons: layout							
Dependent Variable: Extraversion							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	0.028	0.050	1.000	-0.113	0.169
		Unfolding	-0.031	0.050	1.000	-0.171	0.109
		Horizontal scrolling	0.054	0.050	1.000	-0.087	0.196
		Paging	-0.034	0.050	1.000	-0.174	0.106
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.028	0.050	1.000	-0.169	0.113
		Unfolding	-0.060	0.050	1.000	-0.199	0.080
		Horizontal scrolling	0.026	0.050	1.000	-0.114	0.167
		Paging	-0.062	0.050	1.000	-0.202	0.077
	Unfolding	Grid	0.031	0.050	1.000	-0.109	0.171
		Scrolling	0.060	0.050	1.000	-0.080	0.199
		Horizontal scrolling	0.086	0.050	0.847	-0.054	0.226
		Paging	-0.003	0.049	1.000	-0.142	0.136
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.054	0.050	1.000	-0.196	0.087
		Scrolling	-0.026	0.050	1.000	-0.167	0.114
		Unfolding	-0.086	0.050	0.847	-0.226	0.054
		Paging	-0.089	0.050	0.758	-0.229	0.051
	Paging	Grid	0.034	0.050	1.000	-0.106	0.174
		Scrolling	0.062	0.050	1.000	-0.077	0.202
		Unfolding	0.003	0.049	1.000	-0.136	0.142
		Horizontal scrolling	0.089	0.050	0.758	-0.051	0.229
SP	Grid	Scrolling	-0.024	0.055	1.000	-0.179	0.131
		Unfolding	0.084	0.056	1.000	-0.073	0.242
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.037	0.057	1.000	-0.196	0.122
		Paging	-0.020	0.057	1.000	-0.180	0.139
	Scrolling	Grid	0.024	0.055	1.000	-0.131	0.179
		Unfolding	0.108	0.056	0.525	-0.048	0.265
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.014	0.056	1.000	-0.172	0.145
		Paging	0.003	0.057	1.000	-0.156	0.162
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.084	0.056	1.000	-0.242	0.073
		Scrolling	-0.108	0.056	0.525	-0.265	0.048
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.122	0.057	0.334	-0.282	0.039
		Paging	-0.105	0.057	0.686	-0.266	0.057
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.037	0.057	1.000	-0.122	0.196
		Scrolling	0.014	0.056	1.000	-0.145	0.172
		Unfolding	0.122	0.057	0.334	-0.039	0.282
		Paging	0.017	0.058	1.000	-0.146	0.180
	Paging	Grid	0.020	0.057	1.000	-0.139	0.180
		Scrolling	-0.003	0.057	1.000	-0.162	0.156
		Unfolding	0.105	0.057	0.686	-0.057	0.266
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.017	0.058	1.000	-0.180	0.146
Based on estimated marginal means							
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 22: Estimated marginal means for “Extraversion” by device

Pairwise Comparisons: device							
Dependent Variable: Extraversion							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	-0.076	0.053	0.152	-0.180	0.028
	SP	PC	0.076	0.053	0.152	-0.028	0.180
Scrolling	PC	SP	-0.128*	0.052	0.015	-0.231	-0.025
	SP	PC	0.128*	0.052	0.015	0.025	0.231
Unfolding	PC	SP	0.040	0.053	0.454	-0.064	0.144
	SP	PC	-0.040	0.053	0.454	-0.144	0.064
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	-0.168*	0.054	0.002	-0.274	-0.062
	SP	PC	0.168*	0.054	0.002	0.062	0.274
Paging	PC	SP	-0.062	0.054	0.251	-0.168	0.044
	SP	PC	0.062	0.054	0.251	-0.044	0.168
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 23: Estimated marginal means for “Agreeableness” by layout

Pairwise Comparisons: Layout							
Dependent Variable: Agreeableness							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	0.034	0.041	1.000	-0.082	0.149
		Unfolding	0.082	0.041	0.446	-0.033	0.198
		Horizontal scrolling	0.057	0.041	1.000	-0.059	0.173
		Paging	0.057	0.041	1.000	-0.058	0.173
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.034	0.041	1.000	-0.149	0.082
		Unfolding	0.049	0.041	1.000	-0.066	0.163
		Horizontal scrolling	0.023	0.041	1.000	-0.092	0.138
		Paging	0.024	0.041	1.000	-0.091	0.139
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.082	0.041	0.446	-0.198	0.033
		Scrolling	-0.049	0.041	1.000	-0.163	0.066
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.026	0.041	1.000	-0.141	0.089
		Paging	-0.025	0.041	1.000	-0.139	0.089
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.057	0.041	1.000	-0.173	0.059
		Scrolling	-0.023	0.041	1.000	-0.138	0.092
		Unfolding	0.026	0.041	1.000	-0.089	0.141
		Paging	0.001	0.041	1.000	-0.114	0.116
	Paging	Grid	-0.057	0.041	1.000	-0.173	0.058
		Scrolling	-0.024	0.041	1.000	-0.139	0.091
		Unfolding	0.025	0.041	1.000	-0.089	0.139
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.001	0.041	1.000	-0.116	0.114
SP	Grid	Scrolling	0.091	0.045	0.441	-0.036	0.219
		Unfolding	0.110	0.046	0.172	-0.020	0.239
		Horizontal scrolling	0.094	0.046	0.422	-0.036	0.224
		Paging	0.068	0.047	1.000	-0.064	0.199
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.091	0.045	0.441	-0.219	0.036
		Unfolding	0.019	0.046	1.000	-0.110	0.147
		Horizontal scrolling	0.003	0.046	1.000	-0.127	0.132
		Paging	-0.024	0.047	1.000	-0.154	0.107
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.110	0.046	0.172	-0.239	0.020
		Scrolling	-0.019	0.046	1.000	-0.147	0.110
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.016	0.047	1.000	-0.147	0.116
		Paging	-0.042	0.047	1.000	-0.175	0.091
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.094	0.046	0.422	-0.224	0.036
		Scrolling	-0.003	0.046	1.000	-0.132	0.127
		Unfolding	0.016	0.047	1.000	-0.116	0.147
		Paging	-0.026	0.047	1.000	-0.160	0.107
	Paging	Grid	-0.068	0.047	1.000	-0.199	0.064
		Scrolling	0.024	0.047	1.000	-0.107	0.154
		Unfolding	0.042	0.047	1.000	-0.091	0.175
		Horizontal scrolling	0.026	0.047	1.000	-0.107	0.160
Based on estimated marginal means							
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 24: Estimated marginal means for “Agreeableness” by device

Pairwise Comparisons: Device							
Dependent Variable: Agreeableness							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	-0.064	0.044	0.144	-0.149	0.022
	SP	PC	0.064	0.044	0.144	-0.022	0.149
Scrolling	PC	SP	-0.006	0.043	0.891	-0.090	0.079
	SP	PC	0.006	0.043	0.891	-0.079	0.090
Unfolding	PC	SP	-0.036	0.044	0.408	-0.122	0.049
	SP	PC	0.036	0.044	0.408	-0.049	0.122
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	-0.026	0.044	0.555	-0.113	0.061
	SP	PC	0.026	0.044	0.555	-0.061	0.113
Paging	PC	SP	-0.053	0.045	0.232	-0.141	0.034
	SP	PC	0.053	0.045	0.232	-0.034	0.141
Based on estimated marginal means							
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 25: Estimated marginal means for “Conscientiousness” by layout

Pairwise Comparisons: Layout								
Dependent Variable: Conscientiousness								
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
PC	Grid	Scrolling	-0.019	0.042	1.000	-0.137	0.098	
		Unfolding	0.042	0.041	1.000	-0.074	0.159	
		Horizontal scrolling	0.044	0.042	1.000	-0.074	0.162	
		Paging	-0.067	0.042	1.000	-0.184	0.050	
	Scrolling	Grid	0.019	0.042	1.000	-0.098	0.137	
		Unfolding	0.062	0.041	1.000	-0.055	0.178	
		Horizontal scrolling	0.063	0.042	1.000	-0.054	0.181	
		Paging	-0.048	0.042	1.000	-0.164	0.069	
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.042	0.041	1.000	-0.159	0.074	
		Scrolling	-0.062	0.041	1.000	-0.178	0.055	
		Horizontal scrolling	0.002	0.042	1.000	-0.115	0.118	
		Paging	-0.109	0.041	0.083	-0.225	0.007	
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.044	0.042	1.000	-0.162	0.074	
		Scrolling	-0.063	0.042	1.000	-0.181	0.054	
		Unfolding	-0.002	0.042	1.000	-0.118	0.115	
		Paging	-0.111	0.042	0.080	-0.228	0.007	
	Paging	Grid	0.067	0.042	1.000	-0.050	0.184	
		Scrolling	0.048	0.042	1.000	-0.069	0.164	
		Unfolding	0.109	0.041	0.083	-0.007	0.225	
		Horizontal scrolling	0.111	0.042	0.080	-0.007	0.228	
	SP	Grid	Scrolling	0.056	0.046	1.000	-0.073	0.186
			Unfolding	0.055	0.047	1.000	-0.076	0.186
			Horizontal scrolling	0.086	0.047	0.682	-0.046	0.219
			Paging	-0.031	0.048	1.000	-0.164	0.103
Scrolling		Grid	-0.056	0.046	1.000	-0.186	0.073	
		Unfolding	-0.002	0.046	1.000	-0.132	0.129	
		Horizontal scrolling	0.030	0.047	1.000	-0.102	0.161	
		Paging	-0.087	0.047	0.654	-0.220	0.046	
Unfolding		Grid	-0.055	0.047	1.000	-0.186	0.076	
		Scrolling	0.002	0.046	1.000	-0.129	0.132	
		Horizontal scrolling	0.031	0.048	1.000	-0.102	0.165	
		Paging	-0.086	0.048	0.741	-0.220	0.049	
Horizontal scrolling		Grid	-0.086	0.047	0.682	-0.219	0.046	
		Scrolling	-0.030	0.047	1.000	-0.161	0.102	
		Unfolding	-0.031	0.048	1.000	-0.165	0.102	
		Paging	-0.117	0.048	0.160	-0.253	0.019	
Paging		Grid	0.031	0.048	1.000	-0.103	0.164	
		Scrolling	0.087	0.047	0.654	-0.046	0.220	
		Unfolding	0.086	0.048	0.741	-0.049	0.220	
		Horizontal scrolling	0.117	0.048	0.160	-0.019	0.253	
Based on estimated marginal means								
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.								

Table 26: Estimated marginal means for “Conscientiousness” by device

Pairwise Comparisons: Device							
Dependent Variable: Conscientiousness							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	0.057	0.044	0.197	-0.030	0.144
	SP	PC	-0.057	0.044	0.197	-0.144	0.030
Scrolling	PC	SP	0.133*	0.044	0.002	0.047	0.218
	SP	PC	-0.133*	0.044	0.002	-0.218	-0.047
Unfolding	PC	SP	0.070	0.044	0.114	-0.017	0.156
	SP	PC	-0.070	0.044	0.114	-0.156	0.017
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	0.099*	0.045	0.028	0.011	0.188
	SP	PC	-0.099*	0.045	0.028	-0.188	-0.011
Paging	PC	SP	0.093*	0.045	0.040	0.004	0.182
	SP	PC	-0.093*	0.045	0.040	-0.182	-0.004
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 27: Estimated marginal means for “Neuroticism” by layout

Pairwise Comparisons: Layout							
Dependent Variable: Neuroticism							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	-0.068	0.045	1.000	-0.196	0.060
		Unfolding	-0.060	0.045	1.000	-0.187	0.067
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.120	0.046	0.086	-0.248	0.008
		Paging	-0.023	0.045	1.000	-0.150	0.105
	Scrolling	Grid	0.068	0.045	1.000	-0.060	0.196
		Unfolding	0.008	0.045	1.000	-0.119	0.134
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.052	0.045	1.000	-0.180	0.075
		Paging	0.045	0.045	1.000	-0.082	0.172
	Unfolding	Grid	0.060	0.045	1.000	-0.067	0.187
		Scrolling	-0.008	0.045	1.000	-0.134	0.119
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.060	0.045	1.000	-0.187	0.067
		Paging	0.037	0.045	1.000	-0.089	0.163
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.120	0.046	0.086	-0.008	0.248
		Scrolling	0.052	0.045	1.000	-0.075	0.180
		Unfolding	0.060	0.045	1.000	-0.067	0.187
		Paging	0.097	0.045	0.320	-0.030	0.224
	Paging	Grid	0.023	0.045	1.000	-0.105	0.150
		Scrolling	-0.045	0.045	1.000	-0.172	0.082
		Unfolding	-0.037	0.045	1.000	-0.163	0.089
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.097	0.045	0.320	-0.224	0.030
SP	Grid	Scrolling	-0.028	0.050	1.000	-0.168	0.112
		Unfolding	-0.017	0.051	1.000	-0.159	0.126
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.042	0.051	1.000	-0.185	0.101
		Paging	0.034	0.052	1.000	-0.110	0.179
	Scrolling	Grid	0.028	0.050	1.000	-0.112	0.168
		Unfolding	0.011	0.050	1.000	-0.131	0.153
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.014	0.051	1.000	-0.157	0.128
		Paging	0.062	0.051	1.000	-0.082	0.206
	Unfolding	Grid	0.017	0.051	1.000	-0.126	0.159
		Scrolling	-0.011	0.050	1.000	-0.153	0.131
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.025	0.051	1.000	-0.170	0.119
		Paging	0.051	0.052	1.000	-0.095	0.197
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.042	0.051	1.000	-0.101	0.185
		Scrolling	0.014	0.051	1.000	-0.128	0.157
		Unfolding	0.025	0.051	1.000	-0.119	0.170
		Paging	0.076	0.052	1.000	-0.070	0.223
	Paging	Grid	-0.034	0.052	1.000	-0.179	0.110
		Scrolling	-0.062	0.051	1.000	-0.206	0.082
		Unfolding	-0.051	0.052	1.000	-0.197	0.095
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.076	0.052	1.000	-0.223	0.070
Based on estimated marginal means							
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 28: Estimated marginal means for “Neuroticism” by device

Pairwise Comparisons: Device							
Dependent Variable: Neuroticism							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	-0.129*	0.048	0.007	-0.223	-0.035
	SP	PC	0.129*	0.048	0.007	0.035	0.223
Scrolling	PC	SP	-0.089	0.048	0.061	-0.182	0.004
	SP	PC	0.089	0.048	0.061	-0.004	0.182
Unfolding	PC	SP	-0.086	0.048	0.075	-0.180	0.009
	SP	PC	0.086	0.048	0.075	-0.009	0.180
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	-0.051	0.049	0.297	-0.146	0.045
	SP	PC	0.051	0.049	0.297	-0.045	0.146
Paging	PC	SP	-0.072	0.049	0.145	-0.168	0.025
	SP	PC	0.072	0.049	0.145	-0.025	0.168
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 29: Estimated marginal means for “Imagination” by layout

Pairwise Comparisons: Layout							
Dependent Variable: Imagination							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	0.007	0.046	1.000	-0.122	0.136
		Unfolding	0.011	0.046	1.000	-0.117	0.139
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.016	0.046	1.000	-0.145	0.113
		Paging	0.004	0.046	1.000	-0.124	0.133
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.007	0.046	1.000	-0.136	0.122
		Unfolding	0.004	0.045	1.000	-0.123	0.131
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.023	0.046	1.000	-0.152	0.105
		Paging	-0.003	0.046	1.000	-0.131	0.125
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.011	0.046	1.000	-0.139	0.117
		Scrolling	-0.004	0.045	1.000	-0.131	0.123
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.028	0.045	1.000	-0.155	0.100
		Paging	-0.007	0.045	1.000	-0.134	0.120
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.016	0.046	1.000	-0.113	0.145
		Scrolling	0.023	0.046	1.000	-0.105	0.152
		Unfolding	0.028	0.045	1.000	-0.100	0.155
		Paging	0.021	0.046	1.000	-0.108	0.149
	Paging	Grid	-0.004	0.046	1.000	-0.133	0.124
		Scrolling	0.003	0.046	1.000	-0.125	0.131
		Unfolding	0.007	0.045	1.000	-0.120	0.134
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.021	0.046	1.000	-0.149	0.108
SP	Grid	Scrolling	-0.033	0.050	1.000	-0.175	0.109
		Unfolding	-0.039	0.051	1.000	-0.183	0.105
		Horizontal scrolling	0.010	0.052	1.000	-0.135	0.155
		Paging	-0.021	0.052	1.000	-0.167	0.126
	Scrolling	Grid	0.033	0.050	1.000	-0.109	0.175
		Unfolding	-0.006	0.051	1.000	-0.149	0.137
		Horizontal scrolling	0.043	0.051	1.000	-0.101	0.187
		Paging	0.012	0.052	1.000	-0.133	0.158
	Unfolding	Grid	0.039	0.051	1.000	-0.105	0.183
		Scrolling	0.006	0.051	1.000	-0.137	0.149
		Horizontal scrolling	0.049	0.052	1.000	-0.097	0.195
		Paging	0.019	0.053	1.000	-0.129	0.166
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.010	0.052	1.000	-0.155	0.135
		Scrolling	-0.043	0.051	1.000	-0.187	0.101
		Unfolding	-0.049	0.052	1.000	-0.195	0.097
		Paging	-0.031	0.053	1.000	-0.179	0.118
	Paging	Grid	0.021	0.052	1.000	-0.126	0.167
		Scrolling	-0.012	0.052	1.000	-0.158	0.133
		Unfolding	-0.019	0.053	1.000	-0.166	0.129
		Horizontal scrolling	0.031	0.053	1.000	-0.118	0.179
Based on estimated marginal means							
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 30: Estimated marginal means for “Imagination” by device

Pairwise Comparisons: Device							
Dependent Variable: Imagination							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	-0.043	0.049	0.376	-0.138	0.052
	SP	PC	0.043	0.049	0.376	-0.052	0.138
Scrolling	PC	SP	-0.083	0.048	0.083	-0.177	0.011
	SP	PC	0.083	0.048	0.083	-0.011	0.177
Unfolding	PC	SP	-0.094	0.048	0.054	-0.189	0.001
	SP	PC	0.094	0.048	0.054	-0.001	0.189
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	-0.017	0.049	0.734	-0.113	0.080
	SP	PC	0.017	0.049	0.734	-0.080	0.113
Paging	PC	SP	-0.068	0.050	0.170	-0.165	0.029
	SP	PC	0.068	0.050	0.170	-0.029	0.165
Based on estimated marginal means							
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

2.2 Tasks performed by computers

Table 31: Estimated marginal means for “Auto completion of text” by layout

Pairwise Comparisons: Layout							
Dependent Variable: Please specify to what extent : Auto completion of text							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	-0.060	0.069	1.000	-0.254	0.134
		Unfolding	-0.046	0.069	1.000	-0.239	0.148
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.025	0.069	1.000	-0.220	0.169
		Paging	-0.015	0.069	1.000	-0.209	0.179
	Scrolling	Grid	0.060	0.069	1.000	-0.134	0.254
		Unfolding	0.014	0.069	1.000	-0.179	0.207
		Horizontal scrolling	0.034	0.069	1.000	-0.159	0.228
		Paging	0.045	0.069	1.000	-0.148	0.238
	Unfolding	Grid	0.046	0.069	1.000	-0.148	0.239
		Scrolling	-0.014	0.069	1.000	-0.207	0.179
		Horizontal scrolling	0.020	0.069	1.000	-0.172	0.213
		Paging	0.031	0.068	1.000	-0.161	0.223
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.025	0.069	1.000	-0.169	0.220
		Scrolling	-0.034	0.069	1.000	-0.228	0.159
		Unfolding	-0.020	0.069	1.000	-0.213	0.172
		Paging	0.011	0.069	1.000	-0.182	0.204
	Paging	Grid	0.015	0.069	1.000	-0.179	0.209
		Scrolling	-0.045	0.069	1.000	-0.238	0.148
		Unfolding	-0.031	0.068	1.000	-0.223	0.161
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.011	0.069	1.000	-0.204	0.182
SP	Grid	Scrolling	-0.093	0.076	1.000	-0.306	0.120
		Unfolding	-0.064	0.077	1.000	-0.280	0.152
		Horizontal scrolling	0.001	0.077	1.000	-0.214	0.217
		Paging	0.127	0.078	1.000	-0.093	0.346
	Scrolling	Grid	0.093	0.076	1.000	-0.120	0.306
		Unfolding	0.029	0.076	1.000	-0.185	0.244
		Horizontal scrolling	0.094	0.076	1.000	-0.120	0.308
		Paging	0.220*	0.078	0.047	0.002	0.438
	Unfolding	Grid	0.064	0.077	1.000	-0.152	0.280
		Scrolling	-0.029	0.076	1.000	-0.244	0.185
		Horizontal scrolling	0.065	0.077	1.000	-0.152	0.282
		Paging	0.191	0.079	0.156	-0.031	0.412
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.001	0.077	1.000	-0.217	0.214
		Scrolling	-0.094	0.076	1.000	-0.308	0.120
		Unfolding	-0.065	0.077	1.000	-0.282	0.152
		Paging	0.126	0.079	1.000	-0.095	0.346
	Paging	Grid	-0.127	0.078	1.000	-0.346	0.093
		Scrolling	-0.220*	0.078	0.047	-0.438	-0.002
		Unfolding	-0.191	0.079	0.156	-0.412	0.031
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.126	0.079	1.000	-0.346	0.095
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 32: Estimated marginal means for “Auto completion of text” by device

Pairwise Comparisons: Device							
Dependent Variable: Please specify to what extent : Auto completion of text							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	-0.036	0.073	0.623	-0.179	0.107
	SP	PC	0.036	0.073	0.623	-0.107	0.179
Scrolling	PC	SP	-0.069	0.072	0.337	-0.211	0.072
	SP	PC	0.069	0.072	0.337	-0.072	0.211
Unfolding	PC	SP	-0.054	0.073	0.460	-0.197	0.089
	SP	PC	0.054	0.073	0.460	-0.089	0.197
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	-0.009	0.073	0.899	-0.153	0.134
	SP	PC	0.009	0.073	0.899	-0.134	0.153
Paging	PC	SP	0.106	0.075	0.156	-0.040	0.252
	SP	PC	-0.106	0.075	0.156	-0.252	0.040
Based on estimated marginal means							
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 33: Estimated marginal means for “Spelling and grammar check” by layout

Pairwise Comparisons: Layout							
Dependent Variable: Please specify to what extent : Spelling and grammar check							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	-0.014	0.067	1.000	-0.203	0.174
		Unfolding	0.015	0.067	1.000	-0.173	0.203
		Horizontal scrolling	0.039	0.068	1.000	-0.151	0.229
		Paging	-0.026	0.067	1.000	-0.214	0.162
	Scrolling	Grid	0.014	0.067	1.000	-0.174	0.203
		Unfolding	0.029	0.067	1.000	-0.158	0.217
		Horizontal scrolling	0.053	0.067	1.000	-0.136	0.242
		Paging	-0.012	0.067	1.000	-0.199	0.176
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.015	0.067	1.000	-0.203	0.173
		Scrolling	-0.029	0.067	1.000	-0.217	0.158
		Horizontal scrolling	0.024	0.067	1.000	-0.165	0.212
		Paging	-0.041	0.066	1.000	-0.228	0.146
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.039	0.068	1.000	-0.229	0.151
		Scrolling	-0.053	0.067	1.000	-0.242	0.136
		Unfolding	-0.024	0.067	1.000	-0.212	0.165
		Paging	-0.065	0.067	1.000	-0.253	0.124
	Paging	Grid	0.026	0.067	1.000	-0.162	0.214
		Scrolling	0.012	0.067	1.000	-0.176	0.199
		Unfolding	0.041	0.066	1.000	-0.146	0.228
		Horizontal scrolling	0.065	0.067	1.000	-0.124	0.253
SP	Grid	Scrolling	-0.022	0.074	1.000	-0.228	0.185
		Unfolding	0.076	0.075	1.000	-0.134	0.286
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.024	0.075	1.000	-0.234	0.185
		Paging	0.252*	0.076	0.009	0.039	0.465
	Scrolling	Grid	0.022	0.074	1.000	-0.185	0.228
		Unfolding	0.097	0.074	1.000	-0.111	0.306
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.003	0.074	1.000	-0.211	0.205
		Paging	0.273*	0.075	0.003	0.062	0.485
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.076	0.075	1.000	-0.286	0.134
		Scrolling	-0.097	0.074	1.000	-0.306	0.111
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.100	0.075	1.000	-0.312	0.111
		Paging	0.176	0.077	0.215	-0.039	0.391
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.024	0.075	1.000	-0.185	0.234
		Scrolling	0.003	0.074	1.000	-0.205	0.211
		Unfolding	0.100	0.075	1.000	-0.111	0.312
		Paging	0.276*	0.076	0.003	0.062	0.491
	Paging	Grid	-0.252*	0.076	0.009	-0.465	-0.039
		Scrolling	-0.273*	0.075	0.003	-0.485	-0.062
		Unfolding	-0.176	0.077	0.215	-0.391	0.039
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.276*	0.076	0.003	-0.491	-0.062
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 34: Estimated marginal means for “Spelling and grammar check” by device

Pairwise Comparisons: Device							
Dependent Variable: Please specify to what extent : Spelling and grammar check							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	0.023	0.071	0.745	-0.116	0.162
	SP	PC	-0.023	0.071	0.745	-0.162	0.116
Scrolling	PC	SP	0.015	0.070	0.826	-0.122	0.153
	SP	PC	-0.015	0.070	0.826	-0.153	0.122
Unfolding	PC	SP	0.083	0.071	0.241	-0.056	0.223
	SP	PC	-0.083	0.071	0.241	-0.223	0.056
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	-0.040	0.072	0.571	-0.181	0.100
	SP	PC	0.040	0.072	0.571	-0.100	0.181
Paging	PC	SP	0.300*	0.072	0.000	0.159	0.442
	SP	PC	-0.300*	0.072	0.000	-0.442	-0.159
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 35: Estimated marginal means for “Selecting a playlist to match my musical preferences” by layout

Pairwise Comparisons: Layout								
Dependent Variable: Please specify to what extent : Selecting a playlist to match my musical preferences								
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
PC	Grid	Scrolling	-0.067	0.067	1.000	-0.257	0.122	
		Unfolding	-0.058	0.067	1.000	-0.246	0.131	
		Horizontal scrolling	0.022	0.068	1.000	-0.168	0.212	
		Paging	-0.023	0.067	1.000	-0.212	0.165	
	Scrolling	Grid	0.067	0.067	1.000	-0.122	0.257	
		Unfolding	0.010	0.067	1.000	-0.178	0.197	
		Horizontal scrolling	0.089	0.067	1.000	-0.101	0.279	
		Paging	0.044	0.067	1.000	-0.144	0.232	
	Unfolding	Grid	0.058	0.067	1.000	-0.131	0.246	
		Scrolling	-0.010	0.067	1.000	-0.197	0.178	
		Horizontal scrolling	0.079	0.067	1.000	-0.109	0.268	
		Paging	0.034	0.067	1.000	-0.153	0.221	
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.022	0.068	1.000	-0.212	0.168	
		Scrolling	-0.089	0.067	1.000	-0.279	0.101	
		Unfolding	-0.079	0.067	1.000	-0.268	0.109	
		Paging	-0.045	0.067	1.000	-0.234	0.144	
	Paging	Grid	0.023	0.067	1.000	-0.165	0.212	
		Scrolling	-0.044	0.067	1.000	-0.232	0.144	
		Unfolding	-0.034	0.067	1.000	-0.221	0.153	
		Horizontal scrolling	0.045	0.067	1.000	-0.144	0.234	
	SP	Grid	Scrolling	-0.037	0.074	1.000	-0.244	0.170
			Unfolding	0.042	0.075	1.000	-0.168	0.252
			Horizontal scrolling	-0.001	0.075	1.000	-0.210	0.209
			Paging	-0.033	0.076	1.000	-0.246	0.180
Scrolling		Grid	0.037	0.074	1.000	-0.170	0.244	
		Unfolding	0.079	0.074	1.000	-0.130	0.288	
		Horizontal scrolling	0.036	0.074	1.000	-0.172	0.245	
		Paging	0.004	0.076	1.000	-0.208	0.216	
Unfolding		Grid	-0.042	0.075	1.000	-0.252	0.168	
		Scrolling	-0.079	0.074	1.000	-0.288	0.130	
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.043	0.075	1.000	-0.254	0.169	
		Paging	-0.075	0.077	1.000	-0.290	0.140	
Horizontal scrolling		Grid	0.001	0.075	1.000	-0.209	0.210	
		Scrolling	-0.036	0.074	1.000	-0.245	0.172	
		Unfolding	0.043	0.075	1.000	-0.169	0.254	
		Paging	-0.032	0.076	1.000	-0.247	0.183	
Paging		Grid	0.033	0.076	1.000	-0.180	0.246	
		Scrolling	-0.004	0.076	1.000	-0.216	0.208	
		Unfolding	0.075	0.077	1.000	-0.140	0.290	
		Horizontal scrolling	0.032	0.076	1.000	-0.183	0.247	
Based on estimated marginal means								
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.								

Table 36: Estimated marginal means for “Selecting a playlist to match my musical preferences” by device

Pairwise Comparisons: Device							
Dependent Variable: Please specify to what extent : Selecting a playlist to match my musical preferences							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	-0.162*	0.071	0.022	-0.301	-0.023
	SP	PC	0.162*	0.071	0.022	0.023	0.301
Scrolling	PC	SP	-0.132	0.070	0.061	-0.270	0.006
	SP	PC	0.132	0.070	0.061	-0.006	0.270
Unfolding	PC	SP	-0.063	0.071	0.379	-0.202	0.077
	SP	PC	0.063	0.071	0.379	-0.077	0.202
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	-0.184*	0.072	0.010	-0.325	-0.044
	SP	PC	0.184*	0.072	0.010	0.044	0.325
Paging	PC	SP	-0.171*	0.072	0.018	-0.314	-0.029
	SP	PC	0.171*	0.072	0.018	0.029	0.314
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 37: Estimated marginal means for “Selecting the best and most efficient route in my GPS navigation app while driving” by layout

Pairwise Comparisons: Layout							
Dependent Variable: Please specify to what extent : Selecting the best and most efficient route in my GPS navigation app while driving							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	-0.112	0.062	0.701	-0.287	0.062
		Unfolding	0.013	0.062	1.000	-0.160	0.187
		Horizontal scrolling	0.042	0.062	1.000	-0.133	0.217
		Paging	-0.104	0.062	0.922	-0.278	0.070
	Scrolling	Grid	0.112	0.062	0.701	-0.062	0.287
		Unfolding	0.126	0.062	0.413	-0.047	0.298
		Horizontal scrolling	0.154	0.062	0.132	-0.020	0.328
		Paging	0.008	0.062	1.000	-0.165	0.181
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.013	0.062	1.000	-0.187	0.160
		Scrolling	-0.126	0.062	0.413	-0.298	0.047
		Horizontal scrolling	0.028	0.062	1.000	-0.145	0.202
		Paging	-0.118	0.061	0.558	-0.290	0.055
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.042	0.062	1.000	-0.217	0.133
		Scrolling	-0.154	0.062	0.132	-0.328	0.020
		Unfolding	-0.028	0.062	1.000	-0.202	0.145
		Paging	-0.146	0.062	0.186	-0.320	0.028
	Paging	Grid	0.104	0.062	0.922	-0.070	0.278
		Scrolling	-0.008	0.062	1.000	-0.181	0.165
		Unfolding	0.118	0.061	0.558	-0.055	0.290
		Horizontal scrolling	0.146	0.062	0.186	-0.028	0.320
SP	Grid	Scrolling	-0.112	0.068	0.995	-0.303	0.079
		Unfolding	-0.071	0.069	1.000	-0.266	0.123
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.095	0.069	1.000	-0.288	0.099
		Paging	-0.181	0.070	0.098	-0.378	0.016
	Scrolling	Grid	0.112	0.068	0.995	-0.079	0.303
		Unfolding	0.041	0.069	1.000	-0.153	0.234
		Horizontal scrolling	0.017	0.069	1.000	-0.175	0.210
		Paging	-0.069	0.070	1.000	-0.265	0.127
	Unfolding	Grid	0.071	0.069	1.000	-0.123	0.266
		Scrolling	-0.041	0.069	1.000	-0.234	0.153
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.023	0.070	1.000	-0.219	0.172
		Paging	-0.110	0.071	1.000	-0.308	0.089
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.095	0.069	1.000	-0.099	0.288
		Scrolling	-0.017	0.069	1.000	-0.210	0.175
		Unfolding	0.023	0.070	1.000	-0.172	0.219
		Paging	-0.086	0.071	1.000	-0.285	0.112
	Paging	Grid	0.181	0.070	0.098	-0.016	0.378
		Scrolling	0.069	0.070	1.000	-0.127	0.265
		Unfolding	0.110	0.071	1.000	-0.089	0.308
		Horizontal scrolling	0.086	0.071	1.000	-0.112	0.285
Based on estimated marginal means							
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 38: Estimated marginal means for “Selecting the best and most efficient route in my GPS navigation app while driving” by device

Pairwise Comparisons: Device							
Dependent Variable: Please specify to what extent : Selecting the best and most efficient route in my GPS navigation app while driving							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	-0.065	0.065	0.321	-0.193	0.063
	SP	PC	0.065	0.065	0.321	-0.063	0.193
Scrolling	PC	SP	-0.064	0.065	0.320	-0.191	0.063
	SP	PC	0.064	0.065	0.320	-0.063	0.191
Unfolding	PC	SP	-0.150*	0.066	0.023	-0.278	-0.021
	SP	PC	0.150*	0.066	0.023	0.021	0.278
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	-0.201*	0.066	0.002	-0.330	-0.072
	SP	PC	0.201*	0.066	0.002	0.072	0.330
Paging	PC	SP	-0.141*	0.067	0.034	-0.273	-0.010
	SP	PC	0.141*	0.067	0.034	0.010	0.273
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 39: Estimated marginal means for “Autonomous driving of a motor vehicle” by layout

Pairwise Comparisons: Layout							
Dependent Variable: Please specify to what extent : Autonomous driving of a motor vehicle							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	-0.097	0.071	1.000	-0.297	0.104
		Unfolding	-0.204*	0.071	0.042	-0.403	-0.004
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.023	0.072	1.000	-0.225	0.178
		Paging	0.003	0.071	1.000	-0.198	0.203
	Scrolling	Grid	0.097	0.071	1.000	-0.104	0.297
		Unfolding	-0.107	0.071	1.000	-0.306	0.092
		Horizontal scrolling	0.073	0.072	1.000	-0.128	0.274
		Paging	0.100	0.071	1.000	-0.100	0.299
	Unfolding	Grid	0.204*	0.071	0.042	0.004	0.403
		Scrolling	0.107	0.071	1.000	-0.092	0.306
		Horizontal scrolling	0.180	0.071	0.115	-0.020	0.380
		Paging	0.206*	0.071	0.036	0.008	0.405
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.023	0.072	1.000	-0.178	0.225
		Scrolling	-0.073	0.072	1.000	-0.274	0.128
		Unfolding	-0.180	0.071	0.115	-0.380	0.020
		Paging	0.026	0.071	1.000	-0.174	0.227
	Paging	Grid	-0.003	0.071	1.000	-0.203	0.198
		Scrolling	-0.100	0.071	1.000	-0.299	0.100
		Unfolding	-0.206*	0.071	0.036	-0.405	-0.008
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.026	0.071	1.000	-0.227	0.174
SP	Grid	Scrolling	-0.275*	0.078	0.005	-0.495	-0.054
		Unfolding	-0.270*	0.080	0.007	-0.493	-0.046
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.299*	0.079	0.002	-0.523	-0.076
		Paging	-0.097	0.081	1.000	-0.324	0.130
	Scrolling	Grid	0.275*	0.078	0.005	0.054	0.495
		Unfolding	0.005	0.079	1.000	-0.217	0.227
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.025	0.079	1.000	-0.247	0.198
		Paging	0.177	0.080	0.274	-0.048	0.403
	Unfolding	Grid	0.270*	0.080	0.007	0.046	0.493
		Scrolling	-0.005	0.079	1.000	-0.227	0.217
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.030	0.080	1.000	-0.255	0.196
		Paging	0.172	0.081	0.344	-0.056	0.401
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.299*	0.079	0.002	0.076	0.523
		Scrolling	0.025	0.079	1.000	-0.198	0.247
		Unfolding	0.030	0.080	1.000	-0.196	0.255
		Paging	0.202	0.081	0.132	-0.027	0.431
	Paging	Grid	0.097	0.081	1.000	-0.130	0.324
		Scrolling	-0.177	0.080	0.274	-0.403	0.048
		Unfolding	-0.172	0.081	0.344	-0.401	0.056
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.202	0.081	0.132	-0.431	0.027
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 40: Estimated marginal means for “Autonomous driving of a motor vehicle” by device

Pairwise Comparisons: Device							
Dependent Variable: Please specify to what extent : Autonomous driving of a motor vehicle							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	0.076	0.075	0.312	-0.071	0.224
	SP	PC	-0.076	0.075	0.312	-0.224	0.071
Scrolling	PC	SP	-0.102	0.075	0.173	-0.248	0.045
	SP	PC	0.102	0.075	0.173	-0.045	0.248
Unfolding	PC	SP	0.010	0.076	0.893	-0.138	0.158
	SP	PC	-0.010	0.076	0.893	-0.158	0.138
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	-0.200*	0.076	0.009	-0.349	-0.050
	SP	PC	0.200*	0.076	0.009	0.050	0.349
Paging	PC	SP	-0.024	0.077	0.756	-0.175	0.127
	SP	PC	0.024	0.077	0.756	-0.127	0.175
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 41: Estimated marginal means for “Diagnosis of my medical status by an AI system” by layout

Pairwise Comparisons: Layout							
Dependent Variable: Please specify to what extent : Diagnosis of my medical status by an AI system							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	-0.092	0.068	1.000	-0.282	0.099
		Unfolding	-0.123	0.068	0.687	-0.313	0.067
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.122	0.068	0.748	-0.314	0.070
		Paging	-0.028	0.068	1.000	-0.218	0.162
	Scrolling	Grid	0.092	0.068	1.000	-0.099	0.282
		Unfolding	-0.031	0.067	1.000	-0.220	0.158
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.030	0.068	1.000	-0.221	0.161
		Paging	0.064	0.067	1.000	-0.126	0.253
	Unfolding	Grid	0.123	0.068	0.687	-0.067	0.313
		Scrolling	0.031	0.067	1.000	-0.158	0.220
		Horizontal scrolling	0.001	0.068	1.000	-0.189	0.192
		Paging	0.095	0.067	1.000	-0.094	0.284
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.122	0.068	0.748	-0.070	0.314
		Scrolling	0.030	0.068	1.000	-0.161	0.221
		Unfolding	-0.001	0.068	1.000	-0.192	0.189
		Paging	0.094	0.068	1.000	-0.097	0.285
	Paging	Grid	0.028	0.068	1.000	-0.162	0.218
		Scrolling	-0.064	0.067	1.000	-0.253	0.126
		Unfolding	-0.095	0.067	1.000	-0.284	0.094
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.094	0.068	1.000	-0.285	0.097
SP	Grid	Scrolling	-0.144	0.074	0.532	-0.352	0.065
		Unfolding	-0.151	0.075	0.454	-0.363	0.061
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.190	0.075	0.118	-0.401	0.022
		Paging	-0.069	0.077	1.000	-0.284	0.146
	Scrolling	Grid	0.144	0.074	0.532	-0.065	0.352
		Unfolding	-0.007	0.075	1.000	-0.218	0.203
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.046	0.075	1.000	-0.257	0.164
		Paging	0.074	0.076	1.000	-0.139	0.288
	Unfolding	Grid	0.151	0.075	0.454	-0.061	0.363
		Scrolling	0.007	0.075	1.000	-0.203	0.218
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.039	0.076	1.000	-0.253	0.175
		Paging	0.082	0.077	1.000	-0.135	0.299
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.190	0.075	0.118	-0.022	0.401
		Scrolling	0.046	0.075	1.000	-0.164	0.257
		Unfolding	0.039	0.076	1.000	-0.175	0.253
		Paging	0.121	0.077	1.000	-0.096	0.337
	Paging	Grid	0.069	0.077	1.000	-0.146	0.284
		Scrolling	-0.074	0.076	1.000	-0.288	0.139
		Unfolding	-0.082	0.077	1.000	-0.299	0.135
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.121	0.077	1.000	-0.337	0.096
Based on estimated marginal means							
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 42: Estimated marginal means for “Diagnosis of my medical status by an AI system” by device

Pairwise Comparisons: Device							
Dependent Variable: Please specify to what extent : Diagnosis of my medical status by an AI system							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	-0.027	0.071	0.705	-0.167	0.113
	SP	PC	0.027	0.071	0.705	-0.113	0.167
Scrolling	PC	SP	-0.079	0.071	0.265	-0.218	0.060
	SP	PC	0.079	0.071	0.265	-0.060	0.218
Unfolding	PC	SP	-0.055	0.072	0.443	-0.196	0.086
	SP	PC	0.055	0.072	0.443	-0.086	0.196
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	-0.095	0.072	0.190	-0.237	0.047
	SP	PC	0.095	0.072	0.190	-0.047	0.237
Paging	PC	SP	-0.068	0.073	0.350	-0.212	0.075
	SP	PC	0.068	0.073	0.350	-0.075	0.212
Based on estimated marginal means							
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

2.3 Statements about online shopping: General

Table 43: Estimated marginal means for “The variety and ease of online shopping sometimes leads me to make purchases that I later find unnecessary” by layout

Pairwise Comparisons: Layout							
Dependent Variable: To what extent do you agree or: The variety and ease of online shopping sometimes leads me to make purchases that I later find unnecessary							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	-0.116	0.084	1.000	-0.353	0.121
		Unfolding	-0.098	0.084	1.000	-0.334	0.138
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.008	0.085	1.000	-0.248	0.232
		Paging	0.011	0.084	1.000	-0.225	0.247
	Scrolling	Grid	0.116	0.084	1.000	-0.121	0.353
		Unfolding	0.018	0.084	1.000	-0.218	0.254
		Horizontal scrolling	0.108	0.086	1.000	-0.133	0.348
		Paging	0.127	0.084	1.000	-0.109	0.363
	Unfolding	Grid	0.098	0.084	1.000	-0.138	0.334
		Scrolling	-0.018	0.084	1.000	-0.254	0.218
		Horizontal scrolling	0.090	0.085	1.000	-0.149	0.329
		Paging	0.109	0.084	1.000	-0.125	0.344
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.008	0.085	1.000	-0.232	0.248
		Scrolling	-0.108	0.086	1.000	-0.348	0.133
		Unfolding	-0.090	0.085	1.000	-0.329	0.149
		Paging	0.019	0.085	1.000	-0.220	0.258
	Paging	Grid	-0.011	0.084	1.000	-0.247	0.225
		Scrolling	-0.127	0.084	1.000	-0.363	0.109
		Unfolding	-0.109	0.084	1.000	-0.344	0.125
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.019	0.085	1.000	-0.258	0.220
SP	Grid	Scrolling	-0.002	0.092	1.000	-0.261	0.257
		Unfolding	0.028	0.093	1.000	-0.235	0.290
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.147	0.093	1.000	-0.409	0.115
		Paging	0.006	0.095	1.000	-0.261	0.273
	Scrolling	Grid	0.002	0.092	1.000	-0.257	0.261
		Unfolding	0.029	0.093	1.000	-0.233	0.291
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.145	0.093	1.000	-0.406	0.116
		Paging	0.008	0.095	1.000	-0.258	0.274
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.028	0.093	1.000	-0.290	0.235
		Scrolling	-0.029	0.093	1.000	-0.291	0.233
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.174	0.094	0.641	-0.439	0.090
		Paging	-0.021	0.096	1.000	-0.291	0.248
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.147	0.093	1.000	-0.115	0.409
		Scrolling	0.145	0.093	1.000	-0.116	0.406
		Unfolding	0.174	0.094	0.641	-0.090	0.439
		Paging	0.153	0.096	1.000	-0.116	0.422
	Paging	Grid	-0.006	0.095	1.000	-0.273	0.261
		Scrolling	-0.008	0.095	1.000	-0.274	0.258
		Unfolding	0.021	0.096	1.000	-0.248	0.291
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.153	0.096	1.000	-0.422	0.116
Based on estimated marginal means							
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 44: Estimated marginal means for “The variety and ease of online shopping sometimes leads me to make purchases that I later find unnecessary” by device

Pairwise Comparisons: Device							
Dependent Variable: To what extent do you agree or: The variety and ease of online shopping sometimes leads me to make purchases that I later find unnecessary							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	-0.216*	0.088	0.015	-0.390	-0.043
	SP	PC	0.216*	0.088	0.015	0.043	0.390
Scrolling	PC	SP	-0.102	0.088	0.248	-0.275	0.071
	SP	PC	0.102	0.088	0.248	-0.071	0.275
Unfolding	PC	SP	-0.090	0.089	0.310	-0.265	0.084
	SP	PC	0.090	0.089	0.310	-0.084	0.265
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	-0.355*	0.090	0.000	-0.532	-0.178
	SP	PC	0.355*	0.090	0.000	0.178	0.532
Paging	PC	SP	-0.221*	0.091	0.015	-0.399	-0.043
	SP	PC	0.221*	0.091	0.015	0.043	0.399
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 45: Estimated marginal means for “User ratings and reviews of products and services can be trusted” by layout

Pairwise Comparisons: Layout							
Dependent Variable: To what extent do you agree or: User ratings and reviews of products and services can be trusted							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	-0.056	0.059	1.000	-0.221	0.108
		Unfolding	-0.050	0.058	1.000	-0.214	0.114
		Horizontal scrolling	0.035	0.059	1.000	-0.132	0.202
		Paging	-0.026	0.058	1.000	-0.189	0.138
	Scrolling	Grid	0.056	0.059	1.000	-0.108	0.221
		Unfolding	0.007	0.058	1.000	-0.157	0.171
		Horizontal scrolling	0.091	0.059	1.000	-0.076	0.258
		Paging	0.031	0.058	1.000	-0.133	0.195
	Unfolding	Grid	0.050	0.058	1.000	-0.114	0.214
		Scrolling	-0.007	0.058	1.000	-0.171	0.157
		Horizontal scrolling	0.085	0.059	1.000	-0.082	0.251
		Paging	0.024	0.058	1.000	-0.139	0.187
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.035	0.059	1.000	-0.202	0.132
		Scrolling	-0.091	0.059	1.000	-0.258	0.076
		Unfolding	-0.085	0.059	1.000	-0.251	0.082
		Paging	-0.060	0.059	1.000	-0.226	0.105
	Paging	Grid	0.026	0.058	1.000	-0.138	0.189
		Scrolling	-0.031	0.058	1.000	-0.195	0.133
		Unfolding	-0.024	0.058	1.000	-0.187	0.139
		Horizontal scrolling	0.060	0.059	1.000	-0.105	0.226
SP	Grid	Scrolling	-0.015	0.064	1.000	-0.195	0.165
		Unfolding	0.079	0.065	1.000	-0.103	0.261
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.067	0.065	1.000	-0.249	0.115
		Paging	-0.108	0.066	1.000	-0.294	0.078
	Scrolling	Grid	0.015	0.064	1.000	-0.165	0.195
		Unfolding	0.094	0.065	1.000	-0.088	0.275
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.052	0.065	1.000	-0.234	0.129
		Paging	-0.093	0.066	1.000	-0.279	0.092
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.079	0.065	1.000	-0.261	0.103
		Scrolling	-0.094	0.065	1.000	-0.275	0.088
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.146	0.065	0.256	-0.330	0.038
		Paging	-0.187	0.067	0.051	-0.375	0.000
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.067	0.065	1.000	-0.115	0.249
		Scrolling	0.052	0.065	1.000	-0.129	0.234
		Unfolding	0.146	0.065	0.256	-0.038	0.330
		Paging	-0.041	0.067	1.000	-0.228	0.146
	Paging	Grid	0.108	0.066	1.000	-0.078	0.294
		Scrolling	0.093	0.066	1.000	-0.092	0.279
		Unfolding	0.187	0.067	0.051	0.000	0.375
		Horizontal scrolling	0.041	0.067	1.000	-0.146	0.228

Based on estimated marginal means

a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.

Table 46: Estimated marginal means for “User ratings and reviews of products and services can be trusted” by device

Pairwise Comparisons: Device	
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Dependent Variable: To what extent do you agree or: User ratings and reviews of products and services can be trusted							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	-0.084	0.061	0.173	-0.204	0.037
	SP	PC	0.084	0.061	0.173	-0.037	0.204
Scrolling	PC	SP	-0.042	0.061	0.492	-0.162	0.078
	SP	PC	0.042	0.061	0.492	-0.078	0.162
Unfolding	PC	SP	0.045	0.062	0.467	-0.076	0.166
	SP	PC	-0.045	0.062	0.467	-0.166	0.076
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	-0.186*	0.063	0.003	-0.309	-0.062
	SP	PC	0.186*	0.063	0.003	0.062	0.309
Paging	PC	SP	-0.166*	0.063	0.009	-0.290	-0.042
	SP	PC	0.166*	0.063	0.009	0.042	0.290
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

2.4 Statements about online shopping: Obstacles

Table 47: Estimated marginal means for “I prefer to tangibly test, see and "feel" the product that I buy” by layout

Pairwise Comparisons: Layout							
Dependent Variable: To what extent do you agree or: I prefer to tangibly test, see and "feel" the product that I buy							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	0.022	0.064	1.000	-0.159	0.202
		Unfolding	0.080	0.064	1.000	-0.100	0.260
		Horizontal scrolling	0.058	0.064	1.000	-0.124	0.239
		Paging	0.146	0.064	0.225	-0.034	0.326
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.022	0.064	1.000	-0.202	0.159
		Unfolding	0.058	0.064	1.000	-0.121	0.237
		Horizontal scrolling	0.036	0.064	1.000	-0.144	0.216
		Paging	0.125	0.064	0.505	-0.054	0.304
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.080	0.064	1.000	-0.260	0.100
		Scrolling	-0.058	0.064	1.000	-0.237	0.121
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.022	0.064	1.000	-0.202	0.157
		Paging	0.067	0.063	1.000	-0.112	0.245
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.058	0.064	1.000	-0.239	0.124
		Scrolling	-0.036	0.064	1.000	-0.216	0.144
		Unfolding	0.022	0.064	1.000	-0.157	0.202
		Paging	0.089	0.064	1.000	-0.091	0.268
	Paging	Grid	-0.146	0.064	0.225	-0.326	0.034
		Scrolling	-0.125	0.064	0.505	-0.304	0.054
		Unfolding	-0.067	0.063	1.000	-0.245	0.112
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.089	0.064	1.000	-0.268	0.091
SP	Grid	Scrolling	0.072	0.070	1.000	-0.125	0.269
		Unfolding	0.060	0.071	1.000	-0.139	0.259
		Horizontal scrolling	0.162	0.071	0.223	-0.037	0.361
		Paging	0.002	0.072	1.000	-0.200	0.205
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.072	0.070	1.000	-0.269	0.125
		Unfolding	-0.012	0.071	1.000	-0.211	0.187
		Horizontal scrolling	0.090	0.071	1.000	-0.108	0.289
		Paging	-0.069	0.072	1.000	-0.272	0.133
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.060	0.071	1.000	-0.259	0.139
		Scrolling	0.012	0.071	1.000	-0.187	0.211
		Horizontal scrolling	0.102	0.072	1.000	-0.099	0.303
		Paging	-0.057	0.073	1.000	-0.262	0.147
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.162	0.071	0.223	-0.361	0.037
		Scrolling	-0.090	0.071	1.000	-0.289	0.108
		Unfolding	-0.102	0.072	1.000	-0.303	0.099
		Paging	-0.160	0.073	0.284	-0.364	0.045
	Paging	Grid	-0.002	0.072	1.000	-0.205	0.200
		Scrolling	0.069	0.072	1.000	-0.133	0.272
		Unfolding	0.057	0.073	1.000	-0.147	0.262
		Horizontal scrolling	0.160	0.073	0.284	-0.045	0.364
Based on estimated marginal means							
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 48: Estimated marginal means for “I prefer to tangibly test, see and "feel" the product that I buy” by device

Pairwise Comparisons: Device							
Dependent Variable: To what extent do you agree or: I prefer to tangibly test, see and "feel" the product that I buy							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	0.083	0.068	0.217	-0.049	0.216
	SP	PC	-0.083	0.068	0.217	-0.216	0.049
Scrolling	PC	SP	0.134*	0.067	0.047	0.002	0.265
	SP	PC	-0.134*	0.067	0.047	-0.265	-0.002
Unfolding	PC	SP	0.064	0.068	0.347	-0.069	0.197
	SP	PC	-0.064	0.068	0.347	-0.197	0.069
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	0.188*	0.068	0.006	0.055	0.321
	SP	PC	-0.188*	0.068	0.006	-0.321	-0.055
Paging	PC	SP	-0.060	0.069	0.381	-0.196	0.075
	SP	PC	0.060	0.069	0.381	-0.075	0.196
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 49: Estimated marginal means for “Long delivery times deter me from making an on-line purchase” by layout

Pairwise Comparisons: Layout							
Dependent Variable: To what extent do you agree or: Long delivery times deter me from making an on-line purchase							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	-0.083	0.069	1.000	-0.277	0.112
		Unfolding	0.038	0.069	1.000	-0.156	0.232
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.106	0.070	1.000	-0.303	0.090
		Paging	-0.145	0.069	0.352	-0.339	0.048
	Scrolling	Grid	0.083	0.069	1.000	-0.112	0.277
		Unfolding	0.121	0.069	0.801	-0.073	0.314
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.024	0.069	1.000	-0.219	0.171
		Paging	-0.063	0.069	1.000	-0.256	0.130
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.038	0.069	1.000	-0.232	0.156
		Scrolling	-0.121	0.069	0.801	-0.314	0.073
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.144	0.069	0.374	-0.339	0.050
		Paging	-0.183	0.069	0.075	-0.376	0.009
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.106	0.070	1.000	-0.090	0.303
		Scrolling	0.024	0.069	1.000	-0.171	0.219
		Unfolding	0.144	0.069	0.374	-0.050	0.339
		Paging	-0.039	0.069	1.000	-0.233	0.155
	Paging	Grid	0.145	0.069	0.352	-0.048	0.339
		Scrolling	0.063	0.069	1.000	-0.130	0.256
		Unfolding	0.183	0.069	0.075	-0.009	0.376
		Horizontal scrolling	0.039	0.069	1.000	-0.155	0.233
SP	Grid	Scrolling	-0.060	0.076	1.000	-0.272	0.153
		Unfolding	-0.118	0.077	1.000	-0.334	0.097
		Horizontal scrolling	0.055	0.077	1.000	-0.160	0.270
		Paging	-0.109	0.078	1.000	-0.327	0.109
	Scrolling	Grid	0.060	0.076	1.000	-0.153	0.272
		Unfolding	-0.059	0.077	1.000	-0.274	0.156
		Horizontal scrolling	0.115	0.076	1.000	-0.100	0.329
		Paging	-0.049	0.078	1.000	-0.267	0.168
	Unfolding	Grid	0.118	0.077	1.000	-0.097	0.334
		Scrolling	0.059	0.077	1.000	-0.156	0.274
		Horizontal scrolling	0.173	0.077	0.254	-0.044	0.391
		Paging	0.009	0.079	1.000	-0.211	0.230
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.055	0.077	1.000	-0.270	0.160
		Scrolling	-0.115	0.076	1.000	-0.329	0.100
		Unfolding	-0.173	0.077	0.254	-0.391	0.044
		Paging	-0.164	0.078	0.368	-0.384	0.056
	Paging	Grid	0.109	0.078	1.000	-0.109	0.327
		Scrolling	0.049	0.078	1.000	-0.168	0.267
		Unfolding	-0.009	0.079	1.000	-0.230	0.211
		Horizontal scrolling	0.164	0.078	0.368	-0.056	0.384
Based on estimated marginal means							
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 50: Estimated marginal means for “Long delivery times deter me from making an on-line purchase” by device

Pairwise Comparisons: Device							
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Dependent Variable: To what extent do you agree or: Long delivery times deter me from making an on-line purchase							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	-0.063	0.073	0.390	-0.205	0.080
	SP	PC	0.063	0.073	0.390	-0.080	0.205
Scrolling	PC	SP	-0.040	0.072	0.584	-0.181	0.102
	SP	PC	0.040	0.072	0.584	-0.102	0.181
Unfolding	PC	SP	-0.219*	0.073	0.003	-0.363	-0.075
	SP	PC	0.219*	0.073	0.003	0.075	0.363
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	0.099	0.074	0.180	-0.046	0.244
	SP	PC	-0.099	0.074	0.180	-0.244	0.046
Paging	PC	SP	-0.026	0.074	0.726	-0.171	0.120
	SP	PC	0.026	0.074	0.726	-0.120	0.171
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 51: Estimated marginal means for “I have trust concerns about receiving or returning goods” by layout

Pairwise Comparisons: Layout							
Dependent Variable: To what extent do you agree or: I have trust concerns about receiving or returning goods							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	0.019	0.068	1.000	-0.173	0.211
		Unfolding	0.112	0.068	1.000	-0.079	0.303
		Horizontal scrolling	0.025	0.069	1.000	-0.168	0.219
		Paging	0.092	0.068	1.000	-0.100	0.283
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.019	0.068	1.000	-0.211	0.173
		Unfolding	0.092	0.068	1.000	-0.098	0.283
		Horizontal scrolling	0.006	0.069	1.000	-0.187	0.198
		Paging	0.072	0.068	1.000	-0.118	0.263
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.112	0.068	1.000	-0.303	0.079
		Scrolling	-0.092	0.068	1.000	-0.283	0.098
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.087	0.068	1.000	-0.278	0.105
		Paging	-0.020	0.068	1.000	-0.210	0.169
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.025	0.069	1.000	-0.219	0.168
		Scrolling	-0.006	0.069	1.000	-0.198	0.187
		Unfolding	0.087	0.068	1.000	-0.105	0.278
		Paging	0.066	0.068	1.000	-0.126	0.258
	Paging	Grid	-0.092	0.068	1.000	-0.283	0.100
		Scrolling	-0.072	0.068	1.000	-0.263	0.118
		Unfolding	0.020	0.068	1.000	-0.169	0.210
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.066	0.068	1.000	-0.258	0.126
SP	Grid	Scrolling	-0.025	0.075	1.000	-0.234	0.185
		Unfolding	0.035	0.076	1.000	-0.177	0.247
		Horizontal scrolling	0.090	0.076	1.000	-0.122	0.303
		Paging	0.094	0.077	1.000	-0.121	0.310
	Scrolling	Grid	0.025	0.075	1.000	-0.185	0.234
		Unfolding	0.060	0.075	1.000	-0.152	0.272
		Horizontal scrolling	0.115	0.076	1.000	-0.097	0.327
		Paging	0.119	0.076	1.000	-0.096	0.334
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.035	0.076	1.000	-0.247	0.177
		Scrolling	-0.060	0.075	1.000	-0.272	0.152
		Horizontal scrolling	0.055	0.076	1.000	-0.159	0.270
		Paging	0.059	0.077	1.000	-0.158	0.277
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.090	0.076	1.000	-0.303	0.122
		Scrolling	-0.115	0.076	1.000	-0.327	0.097
		Unfolding	-0.055	0.076	1.000	-0.270	0.159
		Paging	0.004	0.078	1.000	-0.214	0.222
	Paging	Grid	-0.094	0.077	1.000	-0.310	0.121
		Scrolling	-0.119	0.076	1.000	-0.334	0.096
		Unfolding	-0.059	0.077	1.000	-0.277	0.158
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.004	0.078	1.000	-0.222	0.214
Based on estimated marginal means							
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 52: Estimated marginal means for “I have trust concerns about receiving or returning goods” by device

Pairwise Comparisons: Device							
Dependent Variable: To what extent do you agree or: I have trust concerns about receiving or returning goods							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	-0.002	0.072	0.973	-0.143	0.138
	SP	PC	0.002	0.072	0.973	-0.138	0.143
Scrolling	PC	SP	-0.046	0.071	0.515	-0.186	0.093
	SP	PC	0.046	0.071	0.515	-0.093	0.186
Unfolding	PC	SP	-0.079	0.072	0.273	-0.220	0.062
	SP	PC	0.079	0.072	0.273	-0.062	0.220
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	0.063	0.073	0.388	-0.080	0.206
	SP	PC	-0.063	0.073	0.388	-0.206	0.080
Paging	PC	SP	0.001	0.073	0.994	-0.143	0.144
	SP	PC	-0.001	0.073	0.994	-0.144	0.143
Based on estimated marginal means							
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 53: Estimated marginal means for “I’m unable to buy online because I do not have a credit card” by layout

Pairwise Comparisons: Layout							
Dependent Variable: To what extent do you agree or: I’m unable to buy online because I do not have a credit card							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	0.008	0.082	1.000	-0.222	0.237
		Unfolding	0.027	0.082	1.000	-0.202	0.256
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.078	0.082	1.000	-0.309	0.153
		Paging	0.169	0.081	0.379	-0.060	0.398
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.008	0.082	1.000	-0.237	0.222
		Unfolding	0.019	0.081	1.000	-0.208	0.247
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.085	0.082	1.000	-0.315	0.144
		Paging	0.161	0.081	0.461	-0.066	0.388
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.027	0.082	1.000	-0.256	0.202
		Scrolling	-0.019	0.081	1.000	-0.247	0.208
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.105	0.082	1.000	-0.334	0.125
		Paging	0.142	0.081	0.784	-0.085	0.369
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.078	0.082	1.000	-0.153	0.309
		Scrolling	0.085	0.082	1.000	-0.144	0.315
		Unfolding	0.105	0.082	1.000	-0.125	0.334
		Paging	0.247*	0.082	0.025	0.018	0.476
	Paging	Grid	-0.169	0.081	0.379	-0.398	0.060
		Scrolling	-0.161	0.081	0.461	-0.388	0.066
		Unfolding	-0.142	0.081	0.784	-0.369	0.085
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.247*	0.082	0.025	-0.476	-0.018
SP	Grid	Scrolling	0.061	0.089	1.000	-0.189	0.312
		Unfolding	0.065	0.090	1.000	-0.189	0.319
		Horizontal scrolling	0.102	0.091	1.000	-0.153	0.356
		Paging	0.201	0.092	0.285	-0.057	0.458
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.061	0.089	1.000	-0.312	0.189
		Unfolding	0.004	0.090	1.000	-0.249	0.257
		Horizontal scrolling	0.040	0.090	1.000	-0.213	0.294
		Paging	0.140	0.091	1.000	-0.117	0.396
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.065	0.090	1.000	-0.319	0.189
		Scrolling	-0.004	0.090	1.000	-0.257	0.249
		Horizontal scrolling	0.036	0.091	1.000	-0.221	0.293
		Paging	0.136	0.092	1.000	-0.124	0.395
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.102	0.091	1.000	-0.356	0.153
		Scrolling	-0.040	0.090	1.000	-0.294	0.213
		Unfolding	-0.036	0.091	1.000	-0.293	0.221
		Paging	0.099	0.093	1.000	-0.161	0.360
	Paging	Grid	-0.201	0.092	0.285	-0.458	0.057
		Scrolling	-0.140	0.091	1.000	-0.396	0.117
		Unfolding	-0.136	0.092	1.000	-0.395	0.124
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.099	0.093	1.000	-0.360	0.161
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 54: Estimated marginal means for “I’m unable to buy online because I do not have a credit card” by device

Pairwise Comparisons: Device							
Dependent Variable: To what extent do you agree or: I’m unable to buy online because I do not have a credit card							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	-0.191*	0.086	0.026	-0.360	-0.022
	SP	PC	0.191*	0.086	0.026	0.022	0.360
Scrolling	PC	SP	-0.137	0.085	0.106	-0.304	0.029
	SP	PC	0.137	0.085	0.106	-0.029	0.304
Unfolding	PC	SP	-0.153	0.086	0.077	-0.322	0.016
	SP	PC	0.153	0.086	0.077	-0.016	0.322
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	-0.012	0.087	0.894	-0.183	0.159
	SP	PC	0.012	0.087	0.894	-0.159	0.183
Paging	PC	SP	-0.159	0.087	0.069	-0.330	0.012
	SP	PC	0.159	0.087	0.069	-0.012	0.330
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 55: Estimated marginal means for “I am concerned about website security while shopping online” by layout

Pairwise Comparisons: Layout							
Dependent Variable: To what extent do you agree or: I am concerned about website security while shopping online							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	-0.085	0.071	1.000	-0.285	0.116
		Unfolding	-0.090	0.071	1.000	-0.290	0.110
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.075	0.072	1.000	-0.278	0.127
		Paging	-0.139	0.071	0.502	-0.339	0.060
	Scrolling	Grid	0.085	0.071	1.000	-0.116	0.285
		Unfolding	-0.005	0.071	1.000	-0.204	0.193
		Horizontal scrolling	0.009	0.072	1.000	-0.192	0.211
		Paging	-0.055	0.071	1.000	-0.254	0.144
	Unfolding	Grid	0.090	0.071	1.000	-0.110	0.290
		Scrolling	0.005	0.071	1.000	-0.193	0.204
		Horizontal scrolling	0.015	0.071	1.000	-0.186	0.215
		Paging	-0.049	0.071	1.000	-0.247	0.149
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.075	0.072	1.000	-0.127	0.278
		Scrolling	-0.009	0.072	1.000	-0.211	0.192
		Unfolding	-0.015	0.071	1.000	-0.215	0.186
		Paging	-0.064	0.071	1.000	-0.265	0.137
	Paging	Grid	0.139	0.071	0.502	-0.060	0.339
		Scrolling	0.055	0.071	1.000	-0.144	0.254
		Unfolding	0.049	0.071	1.000	-0.149	0.247
		Horizontal scrolling	0.064	0.071	1.000	-0.137	0.265
SP	Grid	Scrolling	-0.067	0.078	1.000	-0.287	0.152
		Unfolding	-0.026	0.079	1.000	-0.248	0.196
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.021	0.079	1.000	-0.243	0.201
		Paging	-0.042	0.080	1.000	-0.267	0.183
	Scrolling	Grid	0.067	0.078	1.000	-0.152	0.287
		Unfolding	0.042	0.079	1.000	-0.179	0.263
		Horizontal scrolling	0.047	0.079	1.000	-0.175	0.268
		Paging	0.026	0.080	1.000	-0.199	0.250
	Unfolding	Grid	0.026	0.079	1.000	-0.196	0.248
		Scrolling	-0.042	0.079	1.000	-0.263	0.179
		Horizontal scrolling	0.005	0.080	1.000	-0.219	0.229
		Paging	-0.016	0.081	1.000	-0.243	0.211
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.021	0.079	1.000	-0.201	0.243
		Scrolling	-0.047	0.079	1.000	-0.268	0.175
		Unfolding	-0.005	0.080	1.000	-0.229	0.219
		Paging	-0.021	0.081	1.000	-0.248	0.206
	Paging	Grid	0.042	0.080	1.000	-0.183	0.267
		Scrolling	-0.026	0.080	1.000	-0.250	0.199
		Unfolding	0.016	0.081	1.000	-0.211	0.243
		Horizontal scrolling	0.021	0.081	1.000	-0.206	0.248
Based on estimated marginal means							
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 56: Estimated marginal means for “I am concerned about website security while shopping online” by device

Pairwise Comparisons: Device	
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Dependent Variable: To what extent do you agree or: I am concerned about website security while shopping online							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	0.011	0.075	0.883	-0.136	0.158
	SP	PC	-0.011	0.075	0.883	-0.158	0.136
Scrolling	PC	SP	0.028	0.074	0.703	-0.118	0.174
	SP	PC	-0.028	0.074	0.703	-0.174	0.118
Unfolding	PC	SP	0.075	0.075	0.317	-0.072	0.223
	SP	PC	-0.075	0.075	0.317	-0.223	0.072
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	0.066	0.076	0.389	-0.084	0.215
	SP	PC	-0.066	0.076	0.389	-0.215	0.084
Paging	PC	SP	0.109	0.076	0.155	-0.041	0.259
	SP	PC	-0.109	0.076	0.155	-0.259	0.041

Based on estimated marginal means

a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.

Table 57: Estimated marginal means for “I am concerned about the privacy of personal data while shopping online” by layout

Pairwise Comparisons: Layout							
Dependent Variable: To what extent do you agree or: I am concerned about the privacy of personal data while shopping online							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	-0.003	0.071	1.000	-0.203	0.197
		Unfolding	-0.014	0.071	1.000	-0.213	0.186
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.033	0.072	1.000	-0.235	0.169
		Paging	-0.147	0.071	0.387	-0.347	0.053
	Scrolling	Grid	0.003	0.071	1.000	-0.197	0.203
		Unfolding	-0.011	0.071	1.000	-0.209	0.188
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.030	0.072	1.000	-0.231	0.171
		Paging	-0.144	0.071	0.420	-0.343	0.055
	Unfolding	Grid	0.014	0.071	1.000	-0.186	0.213
		Scrolling	0.011	0.071	1.000	-0.188	0.209
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.019	0.071	1.000	-0.220	0.181
		Paging	-0.133	0.070	0.585	-0.331	0.065
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.033	0.072	1.000	-0.169	0.235
		Scrolling	0.030	0.072	1.000	-0.171	0.231
		Unfolding	0.019	0.071	1.000	-0.181	0.220
		Paging	-0.114	0.071	1.000	-0.314	0.086
	Paging	Grid	0.147	0.071	0.387	-0.053	0.347
		Scrolling	0.144	0.071	0.420	-0.055	0.343
		Unfolding	0.133	0.070	0.585	-0.065	0.331
		Horizontal scrolling	0.114	0.071	1.000	-0.086	0.314
SP	Grid	Scrolling	0.077	0.078	1.000	-0.141	0.296
		Unfolding	0.010	0.079	1.000	-0.211	0.231
		Horizontal scrolling	0.129	0.079	1.000	-0.092	0.351
		Paging	0.016	0.080	1.000	-0.208	0.240
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.077	0.078	1.000	-0.296	0.141
		Unfolding	-0.067	0.078	1.000	-0.287	0.153
		Horizontal scrolling	0.052	0.079	1.000	-0.169	0.273
		Paging	-0.061	0.080	1.000	-0.285	0.163
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.010	0.079	1.000	-0.231	0.211
		Scrolling	0.067	0.078	1.000	-0.153	0.287
		Horizontal scrolling	0.119	0.080	1.000	-0.104	0.342
		Paging	0.006	0.081	1.000	-0.221	0.232
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.129	0.079	1.000	-0.351	0.092
		Scrolling	-0.052	0.079	1.000	-0.273	0.169
		Unfolding	-0.119	0.080	1.000	-0.342	0.104
		Paging	-0.113	0.081	1.000	-0.340	0.113
	Paging	Grid	-0.016	0.080	1.000	-0.240	0.208
		Scrolling	0.061	0.080	1.000	-0.163	0.285
		Unfolding	-0.006	0.081	1.000	-0.232	0.221
		Horizontal scrolling	0.113	0.081	1.000	-0.113	0.340
Based on estimated marginal means							
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 58: Estimated marginal means for “I am concerned about the privacy of personal data while shopping online” by device

Pairwise Comparisons: Device							
Dependent Variable: To what extent do you agree or: I am concerned about the privacy of personal data while shopping online							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	-0.019	0.075	0.797	-0.166	0.127
	SP	PC	0.019	0.075	0.797	-0.127	0.166
Scrolling	PC	SP	0.061	0.074	0.411	-0.085	0.207
	SP	PC	-0.061	0.074	0.411	-0.207	0.085
Unfolding	PC	SP	0.005	0.075	0.949	-0.142	0.152
	SP	PC	-0.005	0.075	0.949	-0.152	0.142
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	0.143	0.076	0.059	-0.006	0.292
	SP	PC	-0.143	0.076	0.059	-0.292	0.006
Paging	PC	SP	0.144	0.076	0.060	-0.006	0.293
	SP	PC	-0.144	0.076	0.060	-0.293	0.006
Based on estimated marginal means							
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 59: Estimated marginal means for “I lack the necessary digital skills to shop online” by layout

Pairwise Comparisons: Layout							
Dependent Variable: To what extent do you agree or: I lack the necessary digital skills to shop online							
Device	(I) Experimental cell	(J) Experimental cell	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PC	Grid	Scrolling	0.169	0.077	0.284	-0.047	0.385
		Unfolding	0.080	0.077	1.000	-0.136	0.295
		Horizontal scrolling	0.082	0.078	1.000	-0.137	0.300
		Paging	0.060	0.077	1.000	-0.156	0.275
	Scrolling	Grid	-0.169	0.077	0.284	-0.385	0.047
		Unfolding	-0.089	0.076	1.000	-0.304	0.125
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.087	0.077	1.000	-0.305	0.130
		Paging	-0.109	0.076	1.000	-0.324	0.105
	Unfolding	Grid	-0.080	0.077	1.000	-0.295	0.136
		Scrolling	0.089	0.076	1.000	-0.125	0.304
		Horizontal scrolling	0.002	0.077	1.000	-0.215	0.218
		Paging	-0.020	0.076	1.000	-0.234	0.194
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	-0.082	0.078	1.000	-0.300	0.137
		Scrolling	0.087	0.077	1.000	-0.130	0.305
		Unfolding	-0.002	0.077	1.000	-0.218	0.215
		Paging	-0.022	0.077	1.000	-0.239	0.195
	Paging	Grid	-0.060	0.077	1.000	-0.275	0.156
		Scrolling	0.109	0.076	1.000	-0.105	0.324
		Unfolding	0.020	0.076	1.000	-0.194	0.234
		Horizontal scrolling	0.022	0.077	1.000	-0.195	0.239
SP	Grid	Scrolling	-0.077	0.084	1.000	-0.313	0.159
		Unfolding	-0.190	0.085	0.252	-0.429	0.048
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.111	0.085	1.000	-0.350	0.129
		Paging	-0.007	0.086	1.000	-0.249	0.236
	Scrolling	Grid	0.077	0.084	1.000	-0.159	0.313
		Unfolding	-0.113	0.085	1.000	-0.351	0.125
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.033	0.085	1.000	-0.272	0.206
		Paging	0.070	0.086	1.000	-0.172	0.313
	Unfolding	Grid	0.190	0.085	0.252	-0.048	0.429
		Scrolling	0.113	0.085	1.000	-0.125	0.351
		Horizontal scrolling	0.080	0.086	1.000	-0.162	0.321
		Paging	0.183	0.087	0.353	-0.061	0.428
	Horizontal scrolling	Grid	0.111	0.085	1.000	-0.129	0.350
		Scrolling	0.033	0.085	1.000	-0.206	0.272
		Unfolding	-0.080	0.086	1.000	-0.321	0.162
		Paging	0.104	0.087	1.000	-0.142	0.349
	Paging	Grid	0.007	0.086	1.000	-0.236	0.249
		Scrolling	-0.070	0.086	1.000	-0.313	0.172
		Unfolding	-0.183	0.087	0.353	-0.428	0.061
		Horizontal scrolling	-0.104	0.087	1.000	-0.349	0.142
Based on estimated marginal means							
a. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							

Table 60: Estimated marginal means for “I lack the necessary digital skills to shop online” by device

Pairwise Comparisons: Device							
Dependent Variable: To what extent do you agree or: I lack the necessary digital skills to shop online							
Experimental cell	(I) Device	(J) Device	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Grid	PC	SP	0.203*	0.081	0.012	0.045	0.362
	SP	PC	-0.203*	0.081	0.012	-0.362	-0.045
Scrolling	PC	SP	-0.043	0.080	0.593	-0.200	0.115
	SP	PC	0.043	0.080	0.593	-0.115	0.200
Unfolding	PC	SP	-0.067	0.081	0.410	-0.226	0.092
	SP	PC	0.067	0.081	0.410	-0.092	0.226
Horizontal scrolling	PC	SP	0.011	0.082	0.894	-0.150	0.172
	SP	PC	-0.011	0.082	0.894	-0.172	0.150
Paging	PC	SP	0.137	0.083	0.097	-0.025	0.299
	SP	PC	-0.137	0.083	0.097	-0.299	0.025
Based on estimated marginal means							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.							